

Antigua and Barbuda: National Plan for the Management of the System of Protected Areas

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Revised 24th November, 2021

This report is a deliverable for the Department of Environment, Ministry of Health, Wellness and the Environment, Antigua and Barbuda under The Path to 2020 Project, that aims to implement Objective 1 of Antigua and Barbuda's National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (2014 – 2025): *A national system, including protected areas, for the management and conservation of biodiversity conservation is developed and established.*

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Abbreviations

AB	Antigua and Barbuda
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CLNP	Codrington Lagoon National Park
DOE	Department of Environment
EAG	Environmental Awareness Group
EIMAS	Environmental Information Management and Advisory System
EPAs	Environmental Protection Areas
EPMA	Environmental Protection and Management Act
Est.	Established
GEF	Global Environmental Facility
IUCN	World Conservation Union
MTDS	Medium Term Development Strategy
PA	Protected Areas
PACM	Protected Areas Coordinating Mechanism
METT	Management Effectiveness Tracking Tool
NBSAP	National Biodiversity Strategic Action Plan
NDNP	Nelson's Dockyard National Park
NEMMA	Northeast Marine Management Area
NPA	National Parks Authority
NPSPA	National Plan for the System of Protected Areas
SDD	Sustainable Development Dimensions
SIRF	Sustainable Island Resource Framework
SIRMM	Sustainable Island Resource Management Mechanism
SIRMZP	Sustainable Island Resource Management Zoning Plan
SMMA	Shekerley Mountains Management Area
SPPA	Systems Plan for Protected Areas
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WCPA	World Commission on Protected Areas
WWF	World Wildlife Fund

Executive Summary

Objectives

This version of the system plan was based on a review of existing information, including the 2010 draft Systems Plan for Protected Areas in Antigua and Barbuda and online consultations with key stakeholders. The prevailing Covid-19 crisis, public health restrictions and border closures, prevented the consultant from visiting the protected area sites and interacting directly with communities adjacent to these protected areas and key staff at the agencies responsible for management of these sites. Questionnaires were used to help gather current information and a series of online sessions to discuss and review draft documents were held.

The objectives of this plan are to:

1. Provide information to better understand the enabling environment for protected areas management; and
2. Identify and address capacity constraints related to the management of the system of protected areas

This national system plan summarises relevant policies, laws, national plans, key institutions, local capacity, information on key specific sites and financing for protected areas management. It also proposes an implementation plan focusing on quality assurance, staffing, training and budget development for improving capacity and effectiveness in managing the system of protected areas.

Key Findings/Elements

1. Management plans for many protected area sites exist; several are in need of updating. The key challenges, as is common elsewhere in the Caribbean, is the recruitment of an adequate number of quality staff and the timely financing for staffing, equipment, infrastructure and operational activities. These will need to be addressed to adequately manage the system of protected areas.
2. Agencies responsible for protected areas or those that implement activities in protected areas, based on a management effectiveness assessment, identified the following capacity constraints:
 - Staffing: All agencies indicated the need for more human resources, even the National Parks Authority which had the highest number of personnel assigned to protected areas management. Some agencies seemed to be greatly under-staffed.
 - Training: All agencies confirmed the need for training or more training of staff.
 - Budget: All agencies needed more funding to support protected areas operations including equipment and infrastructure. Some protected areas seemed to be grossly underfunded.
3. Effective management of protected areas cannot be realized if the three core capacity elements summarized above are not addressed in a timely manner. Also, the main roles

and responsibilities of protected areas agencies must be understood, accepted and discharged efficiently to ensure management effectiveness.

4. Protected area agencies identified the following management activities considered relevant in relation to the protected areas under its care:
 - a. Planning, Management and Administration
 - Protected area policy and implementation
 - Project planning and management
 - Organisational leadership
 - Human resources management
 - Financial resources management
 - Procurement
 - Administrative documentation and reporting
 - Communication and collaboration
 - b. Applied Protected Area Management
 - Managing visitor use (also interpretation and tour guiding)
 - Surveillance and enforcement of laws/regulations
 - Monitoring and research (including impacts, visitor use, policy/ management prescriptions, etc.)
 - Installation of infrastructure or equipment (e.g. signage, trails, visitor use facilities, etc.)
 - Maintenance of site (including habitats and historic sites) or equipment
 - Site restoration/rehabilitation
 - Awareness building and education
 - Engaging adjacent communities including managing conflicts

All of the protected area entities/agencies had varying capacities for implementation of each of the management activities identified above. In a few cases, an agency did not consider that it had the ability or authority to undertake some of the activities.

5. Protected area entities/agencies were asked to identify training needs that they felt were important in helping them to discharge their responsibilities. The results included project planning and management, monitoring and research, installation of infrastructure and equipment, site maintenance and engagement of adjacent communities. Some agencies seemed not to need any training in particular areas which may suggest that they either already have such skills, or have no capacity to undertake the required responsibilities. Monitoring and research were the only role/responsibility where every agency indicated the need for training. The responses suggested that the NGOs required skills that may reside with some of the government agencies which presented an opportunity for closer collaboration and mutual training.
6. An implementation plan is proposed which focuses on building capacity to enable improved management of the system of protected areas in key components that emerged from the responses of protected area entities and review of the literature. The major elements include quality assurance, staffing, training and budget. A schedule of activities for implementation is also proposed.

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Introduction

The Government of Antigua and Barbuda ratified the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) in December 1993. One of the Articles of this Convention (Article 8a); requires that all Parties to the Convention, among other things: “Establish a system of protected areas or areas where special measures need to be taken to conserve biological diversity.” Since the preparation of the first national report to the CBD in 2001, the threats to biodiversity have not really changed, although the extent of the pressure has intensified. The CBD country profile for Antigua and Barbuda (<https://www.cbd.int/countries/profile/?country=ag#facts>) noted the following:

“Threats are mainly anthropogenic and include fragmentation and loss of habitats due to ad hoc development for tourism and housing purposes; overgrazing of vegetation by livestock in the watersheds; deforestation; improper land use practices leading to erosion and desertification and the introduction of invasive alien species that deplete local genetic diversity. The marine biodiversity is also increasingly threatened by habitat destruction, overexploitation, sand mining and destructive fishing methods. Mangroves that function as nurseries, breeding grounds and habitats for both marine and terrestrial wildlife are being destroyed for coastal development, especially that associated with the tourism sector. The threats to agricultural biodiversity are very different from that of the rest of the country’s biodiversity. The main threats are lack of adequate research, lack of *ex situ* facilities, very little protection of intellectual property and the lack of trained personnel for the implementation of approved policy initiatives. Though the overuse and misuse of herbicides and pesticides may also be cited as a concern, this threat has been significantly curtailed with the implementation of the country’s new pesticide and toxic chemicals act.”

Threats to biodiversity and habitat loss are not likely to be dramatically reduced anytime soon, despite the participation in multilateral environmental agreements and international donor assistance designed to plan and mitigate environmental and biodiversity degradation. Faced with a finite land space, governments of small island developing states in particular, seek economic and social development, often at the expense of environmental integrity, which was a model entrenched from the colonial past. However, recent global and regional assessments of various aspects of biodiversity undertaken by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), among other agencies, have provided a range of science based, policy relevant information accessible to everyone as guidance for reducing biodiversity loss (<https://ipbes.net>).

A major constraint in making significant progress in reducing and reversing biodiversity loss has been the multitude of sometimes conflicting views and understanding on biodiversity among different sectors of society, such as the politicians, land developers, industrialists, agriculturalists/farmers, marginalized communities, economists and conservationists, etc. This pluralistic perspective on biodiversity requires consideration of the use of the concept of biodiversity, a willingness to expand its ambit, and engagement with the multiple and multi-level drivers of change (Pascual *et al*, 2021). In the meantime, focusing on the management of already declared and proposed marine and terrestrial protected areas can ensure that biodiversity and key habitats are conserved. Success in effective management of the national system of protected areas can also help the government to discharge some of its national obligations under the Convention on Biological Diversity and sustain livelihood opportunities for the country.

Importance of Protected Areas

Protected areas in Antigua and Barbuda are also known as national parks, marine reserves, sanctuaries, marine protected areas, forest reserves, historical or cultural heritage sites and protected watersheds. These sites are intended to conserve or wisely use key historical/cultural resources, habitats, species and ecosystem services that provide benefits to the people, now and in the future. These benefits include clean air and water, food, medicinal plants, recreation, education, improved psychological and physical health, livelihoods, climate regulation, and damage mitigation from storms, etc.

The following paragraphs summarise some of the other values or importance of protected areas as promoted by the World Conservation Union (IUCN) in their World Commission on Protected Areas (WCPA) information note for the UNFCCC COP26 in November 2021.

- Terrestrial protected areas store at least 12% of the terrestrial carbon stocks and marine protected areas can mitigate and promote adaptation to climate change through protecting of oceans, which have been a sink of approximately 20-25% of the carbon dioxide in the atmosphere since 2008. If effectively managed, protected and conserved areas can safeguard biodiversity in both the terrestrial and marine realms, and help society cope with climate change impacts by reducing risks associated with climate-related hazards.
- Many Parties to the UNFCCC have identified protected areas as a means of attaining their adaptation and mitigation goals and almost half of these countries have expressed an intention to add new protected areas or expand coverage of those already in place.
- Recognizing that countries will need to create or re-establish jobs quickly during and after the Covid-19 pandemic, WCPA reminds countries that the establishment and management of protected and conserved areas create an opportunity for an economic recovery compatible with climate change and biodiversity goals.

- Investments in protected and conserved areas can achieve multiple goals cost-effectively, including biodiversity protection, climate change mitigation, improvements to physical and mental health, and local economic development.

All of the above points are relevant to Antigua and Barbuda and should help support national policies related to biodiversity conservation and resilience building.

Objectives of this National Plan

A plan for a system of protected areas (system plan) is designed to organize existing knowledge, information and national priorities to enable effective management of biodiversity at key sites across the country, consistent with sustaining local livelihoods, national policy, legislation and international commitments under multilateral environmental agreements. A system plan will also identify key institutions and their roles and capacity required for managing these protected areas, including gaps and constraints with measures to address these issues. The usefulness of a system plan will depend on the level of stakeholder participation in its preparation; the level of political support; institutional commitment for oversight and implementation; and ensuring that the plan is not overly ambitious (in the context of local constraints) and receives adequate and timely budgetary support.

This version of the system plan was based on a review of existing information, including the 2010 draft Systems Plan for Protected Areas in Antigua and Barbuda and online consultations with key stakeholders (Appendix 1). The prevailing Covid-19 crisis, public health restrictions and border closures, prevented the consultant from visiting the PA sites and interacting directly with communities adjacent to the PAs and key PA agencies.

The objectives of this plan are to:

3. Provide information to better understand the enabling environment for protected areas management; and
4. Identify and address capacity constraints related to the management of the system of protected areas

This national system plan summarises relevant policies, laws, national plans, key institutions, local capacity, information on key specific sites and financing for protected areas management. It also proposes an implementation plan focusing on quality assurance, staffing, training and budget development for improving capacity and effectiveness in managing the system of protected areas.

Enabling Environment

Policies

National Strategic Biodiversity Action Plan

There is no stand-alone policy document at the time of writing on PA or biodiversity that has been approved by the Cabinet. However, the Antigua & Barbuda National Strategic Biodiversity Action Plan (NBSAP) for the period 2014-2020 provided overall guidance on the status and management of the country's biodiversity.

The overall objective of the NBSAP is to ensure the biological diversity of Antigua and Barbuda is sustainably and equitably used, protected and conserved so that it contributes positively to the social and economic development of the country. In achieving this objective, the strategy seeks to:

- Establish a national system, including protected areas, for the management and conservation of biodiversity.
- Strengthen the capacity of government natural resources management institutions, as well as non-governmental organizations, to support the objectives and achieve the overall aim of the NBSAP.
- Improve or develop where necessary, enact and enforce ecological legislation providing adequate protection of biological diversity.
- Strengthen public awareness of environmental issues, ecological education and public participation in decision-making.

To achieve these objectives, the strategy proposed by the NBSAP included:

- The sustainable use, protection and conservation of Antigua and Barbuda's biodiversity;
- The effective coordination of all efforts and activities involving the sustainable use, protection and conservation of biodiversity;
- The enforcement of all policies, regulations and legislation affecting these efforts and activities; and
- Developing the knowledge and understanding of the processes governing biodiversity, and the information required to guide and coordinate the activities involving the sustainable use, protection and conservation of biodiversity.

The NBSAP further noted the biodiversity challenges and threats faced by the country as:

- Fragile terrestrial and marine ecosystems such as mangrove wetlands and coral reefs endangered by development projects, pollution and misuse.
- Vulnerability to external economic and natural environmental shocks, such as economic recessions, hurricanes, and climate change. Droughts and hurricanes have severely impacted the bird population, as well as vegetative communities and their dependent fauna.
- Lack of human resource capacity in key biodiversity areas and other related fields.
- Conflicting land use pressures, especially among housing, tourism and agricultural activities.

- Land degradation; and limited institutional capacity to manage the development process because the presence of weak and fragmented land use and development control mechanisms.
- The loss of habitat primarily through the sub-division of lands for housing, tourism development, agriculture and the mining and dredging of sand.
- Fragmentation of natural communities by road-ways, and other man-made features that form a barrier to the movement and dispersal of species.
- The introduction of non-native species, like the Giant African Snail, mongoose, lemon grass and Lion Fish that have a detrimental effect on native wild species by acting as predators, parasites or competitors.
- Overgrazing by livestock mainly goats, sheep, cattle and donkeys that pose a serious threat, particularly in upper watershed areas.
- Pollution as a result of excessive nutrients or sewage discharge into coastal waters, as well as the unregulated and excessive use of pesticides.
- Natural and anthropogenic activities that stress coral reefs (directly and indirectly including through overfishing).

It is important to note that the NBSAP also listed several national biodiversity targets that were aligned with the Convention on Biological Diversity 2020 Aichi Targets. The following national targets are considered crucial to PAs:

- Target 10: By 2015, the multiple anthropogenic pressures on coral reefs, and other vulnerable ecosystems such as the NEMMA, Cades Bay and Codrington Marine Reserves impacted by climate change or ocean acidification are minimized, so as to maintain their integrity and functioning.
- Target 11: A national system, including protected areas, for the management and conservation of biodiversity is developed and established by 2020. This will include, terrestrial areas, wetlands, areas important to migratory species and marine environments.
- Target 14: By 2020 at least two major watershed and mangrove wetland areas are effectively protected.
- Target 18: The formal integration of local communities into the co- management process of Biodiversity in the country by 2020.
- Target 20: The capacity of governmental natural resources management institutions as well as non-governmental organizations, to support the objectives and achieve the overall aim of the NBSAP is strengthened by 2020.

Medium Term Development Strategy

The Government of Antigua and Barbuda has developed a mix of strategies and actions in its path to sustainable development via its Medium-term Development Strategy, 2016-2020. The following four sustainable development dimensions (SDD) were proposed: optimal generation of national wealth; enhanced social cohesion; improved health of the natural environment and sustained historical and cultural assets; and enhanced citizen security.

Seven “flagship” priorities have been identified for implementation over the Medium-Term. Flagship Priority Two, entitled: ‘Strong Tourism Industry as an Economic Anchor’, aims to

reposition Antigua and Barbuda as a premier world class destination that is sufficiently differentiated from other destinations. This requires continued efforts to: expand the room stock; reinvigorate much of the existing aging plant and equipment; engage in adequate marketing; establish adequate air and sea access; improve aesthetics (especially in high tourist traffic areas); enhance and enforce standards and regulations; restore and maintain historical and cultural sites; and protect the environment, including coastal and marine ecosystems.

Specific actions that were proposed, related to protected areas include:

- Further strengthening of coordination arrangements for integrated environmental management;
- Enactment of remaining legislation;
- Review, and adjustment as necessary, of the process for reviewing likely environmental impacts from new prospective development initiatives;
- Continuation of effort to prepare a marine reserve management plan;
- Review and as necessary adjust arrangements for surveillance, review and control of developments that surround historical and cultural sites;
- Enhancing the monitoring and evaluation system of the National Parks Authority.

It is clear from these policy documents that the government has defined its direction and priorities in the context of biodiversity and protected areas management. There is currently no documentation that assesses the extent of achievement of the targets and other priority actions. There is an indication from existing reports and ongoing projects, that some of the key activities have not been completed and others recently started. This could indicate that systemic and institution weaknesses may exist, causing delays.

Legislation

Environmental Protection and Management Act, 2019

The Environmental Protection and Management Act (EPMA) was gazetted on 6th June 2019. It provides for sustainable environmental protection and management of natural resources, the allocation of administrative responsibility for the management of environmental matters; giving effect to Antigua and Barbuda's treaty obligations with respect to the environment and provides the framework financial mechanism to satisfy the requirements of the Act and for other related matters. This Act repealed the earlier 2015 version.

The Act established the Department of Environment (DOE) within the Ministry with responsibility for the Environment, which among other things, in the context of protected areas, is responsible for:

- Developing and implementing policies, programmes and plans for the effective management and conservation of the environment and natural resources consistent with the requirements of the Act;

- Coordinating environmental management functions performed by all governmental and non-governmental entities and statutory authorities in order to achieve the purposes of this Act;
- Undertaking the conservation, protection and management of biodiversity and the wildlife of Antigua and Barbuda including the management and licensing of biodiversity prospecting;
- Collaborating with the appropriate authority to ensure the effective administration and management of any area that is declared to be a protected area;
- Collaboration with the appropriate authority, in the development, implementation and monitoring of management plans and programmes for protected areas on Crown lands declared under this Act.

The DoE has the power to do all things necessary or convenient to be done for the carrying out of its functions under this Act.

Part VIII – A of the Act deals specifically with management of protected areas including defining the management principles, the purposes and procedures for establishment of protected areas on Crown lands and private lands, declaration of protected watersheds and important wetlands, conservation and enforcement. Included in the Schedules of the Act, in the context of protected areas, are the List of Protected Areas Category; Forest Reserves in Antigua and Barbuda; List of Protected Watersheds; List of Important Wetlands; and the List of Protected Wildlife including plants.

This Act strengthens the government’s legislative mandate for the management of biodiversity and protected areas and undoubtedly places the DoE in the position to lead and coordinate operational activities. It is unclear however, why existing national parks were not included in a schedule of designated protected areas or if protected areas designated under other legislation will receive protection or administrative support under the EPMA.

National Parks Act, 1984

The National Parks Act, 1984 and its subsequent amendments provided for the establishment of the National Parks Authority (NPA) and made provisions for the preservation, protection, management and development of the natural physical and ecological resources and the historical and cultural heritage of Antigua and Barbuda. Section 20 in particular, outlines the procedure for the Minister to declare any area of land or water or both land and water to be a National Park.

Section 22 clearly enunciated that no permission, approval, authority, sub-division, lease or permission relating to any land or property whether Crown land or ,otherwise within a Park shall be granted or made by the Central Housing and Planning Authority, the Development Control Authority or the Port Authority, or by anybody purporting to act with delegated authority from any such body unless the prior written approval of the NPA is obtained for that purpose; and if such approval is not obtained, any such action by any such body shall be null and void from the beginning. The NPA may not refuse to grant the approval except where it is satisfied that it is necessary to do so for the better carrying out of its functions under this Act or in order to give effect to a Parks Plan or any part thereof.

It is interesting that no other Act which provides for the declaration of protected areas has such a clause as Section 22. Such an omission suggests that lands in other protected areas may be at risk to conversion for other uses, inconsistent with the purposes for which these protected areas were established.

Fisheries Act, 2006

The Fisheries Act, 2006 and its regulations created an enabling environment for the development and management of fisheries and related matters. Section 53 in particular, gives the Minister the power to declare an area of Antigua and Barbuda waters, and as appropriate, any adjacent or surrounding land, to be a marine reserve. The Act also states that the purpose of such a marine reserve may be to:

1. afford special protection to the flora and fauna of such areas;
2. protect and preserve the natural breeding grounds and habitats of aquatic life, with particular regard to flora and fauna in danger of extinction;
3. to allow for the natural regeneration of aquatic life in areas where such life has been depleted or threatened;
4. promote scientific study and research in respect of such areas; or
5. preserve and enhance the natural beauty of such areas.

Offences and penalties are also specified in Section 53, as well as provision for the establishment of a regulatory authority for marine reserves and including the authorisation of secondment of public officers to provide the staff of any such authority so established. No such authority has so far been established under this Act. Section 76(2)(p) allows the Minister to make regulations for, among other things; the management and protection of marine reserves and fishing priority areas.

Barbuda Land Act, 2007 and Barbuda (Coastal Zoning and Management) Regulations, 2014

Under the jurisdiction of the Barbuda Council, Section 12 of the Act gives the Council power to designate areas of land in Barbuda for national parks, forestry and fisheries, among other things. The Regulations provide for the management of specific coastal areas of Barbuda including the establishment of marine sanctuaries, no-net zones, anchoring and mooring zones, shipping areas and additional types of zones and restrictions on activities as needed, payment of management fees, research and prohibitions in the sanctuaries and zones. It is not clear what amendments to the regulations or schedules have been made since 2014.

National Plans

Sustainable Island Resource Management Zoning Plan

The Sustainable Island Resource Management Zoning Plan (SIRMZP) was adopted by the government in 2012. It serves as the revised National Physical Development Plan that meets the criteria of the Physical Planning Act, 2003. The SIRMZP seeks more specific options to

optimise the productive use of environmental resources while protecting critical ecosystems and promoting the local economic development, notably in the tourism, services, agriculture and the industrial sectors.

The SIRMZP recognized that: “Containment of settlement growth within designated boundaries would not eliminate sprawl but is nevertheless essential to the protection of agricultural lands as well as sensitive environmental areas and ecosystems...”. The document further noted that during consultations “stakeholders agreed that the current land use policies and patterns of land use are not sustainable and do not provide a viable option for accommodating future population growth while at the same time preserving the vital ecosystems of the country”. A recommended approach, among others, was to provide legislative and management capacity for area protection and sustainable use of agricultural lands, watersheds, wetlands, representative samples of biological diversity and other valued heritage resources.

Under its development control guidelines for discrete spatial units, the SIRMZP recommended, in addition to other measures, that Environmental Protection Areas (EPAs) be established consistent with the provisions under Section 54.2 of the Physical Planning Act, 2003. These EPAs must specify “the features that need protection, such as flora, fauna, landscape quality, outstanding physical, ecological, architectural or historic elements, features of scientific interest, natural hazards and other unique characteristics or circumstances of people living or working in the area”. It was also stated that: “... development activities and intensities that are permitted in these areas must be restricted to uses and levels that ensure these critical functions may be maintained”.

Systems Plan for Protected Areas in Antigua and Barbuda

The Final Draft of the Systems Plan for Protected Areas in AB (SPPA) was submitted to the government in December 2010 but had no formal approval by the Cabinet. The SPPA is a comprehensive document that reviewed existing literature at that time and consulted with local stakeholders (although limited in extent), to give a good and still useful rationale for the SPPA, site assessment of existing and proposed PAs, governance structure and institutional challenges, management planning, financial arrangements, capacity building and a proposed legal framework.

Key weaknesses or challenges to PA management at that time were summarized in the SPPA as:

1. The various protected areas exist more or less in isolation of each other and clearly, do not establish a comprehensive framework for a Protected Area System.
2. Boundaries of the PAs are very poorly marked; in most cases, maps of PAs are difficult to find and few persons are aware of the actual boundaries. The marine PAs have had buoy markers, but these are apparently not well maintained.
3. In most of the PA sites there is very little management of the natural resources, although in some cases, historical and cultural aspects are actively managed. The Fisheries Division does monitor fisheries and other resources in its general monitoring programme, but these activities are not directed specifically at the PA system.

4. Apart from the Nelson's Dockyard National Park -
 - No user fees or other kinds of revenue are generated by the PA management for use in the particular PA.
 - Little or no funding has been successfully sought for PA development outside of government support for the respective agencies
5. Apart from the Codrington Lagoon National Park and the NPA, there are no rangers or wardens with specific roles in making sure that PA regulations regarding use of natural resources are being observed and there is very little enforcement.
6. With the exception of data recently generated by the SIRMZP project consultancies, there is very little documented data available on the biodiversity to be conserved in any of the PAs. Except where consultants have been contracted to provide them, management plans for most PAs are non-existent or badly out of date.
7. In some declared PAs, the legal basis for the PA is restricted in scope and is not adequate to properly support the multiple uses of the PA that need to be included and in other cases, the legal authority is not accompanied by the required technical capacity for managing the PAs.
8. So far, despite the adoption of participatory management principles in some of the newer PAs, participation has not been facilitated due to inadequate legal provisions or fears that it will not work effectively, or perhaps will lead to erosion of the agency's authority.
9. There is very little public awareness within the local population about existing PAs and little promotion or educational activity to inform the local population about the country's PAs
10. Since each PA is managed quite separately from the other PAs, there is little opportunity for any sharing of costs or human resources.
11. Few persons have had tertiary level training in areas of PA management or development and this means that with these scarce human resources, some PAs will be left without the required technical expertise.
12. There has been no systematic analysis of the nation's biodiversity.
13. Proposals for additional PAs have not been made on a coordinated basis with the result that some sites are being proposed several times, or areas within already existing PAs are proposed for declaration.
14. Adequate training is lacking as regards the requirements for site type designation. This can lead to some confusion among tourist visitors whose expectations from the name may not be met by what is on the ground.

The SPPA also made the following recommendations for the governance structure to manage the system of PAs that was considered appropriate at that time. These recommendations are summarised below:

1. The System of PAs should operate as a statutory body with clearly defined objectives, and statutes that would give it freedom to collect revenue and to spend it in furtherance of its objectives as well as to set up trust funds or other financial instruments to provide the necessary financial resources to operate and to develop.
2. The System of PAs would comprise both core (centralised) management services for the operation of the system as a whole, as well as individual Site Management Entities for each component PA.

3. The System of PAs would be able to contract out some of its services to be provided by Government personnel or agencies, or to competent NGOs or consultancy firms. This can reduce overheads and provide control on productivity and standards.
4. The System of PAs should embrace the principles of participatory management throughout its own system and towards other stakeholders in the component PAs.
5. The organisation to manage the System of PAs would need a Board of Management that is representative of all the agencies of Government that have a stake in protected areas, as well as the private sector, particularly in the tourism sector, and NGOs involved in conservation or biodiversity management work and that has a high technical competence, reflective of the technical nature of conservation management. The Management Plan for the operation of the NEMMA provides a good model to follow.

The recent enactment of the Environmental Protection and Management Act, 2019 provides the legal framework to achieve many of those recommendations. Subsequent to the SPPA, the following actions were initiated or completed:

- Site specific biodiversity studies/assessments in preparation for management of PAs were undertaken by Consultants and the EAG facilitated by external funding.
- Participatory management and cooperation with adjacent communities and other entities have been ongoing at a few PA sites, with NGOs taking the lead.
- Management plans prepared for at least seven PA sites.
- Strengthening regulations, institutions and financing mechanisms for the national Protected Areas System.
- Expansion of protected areas in support of species conservation.
- Pilot livelihood financing mechanisms that support conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity and plant genetic resources in the proposed Shekerley Mountain Management Area.

Institutional Framework

Institutions

The SPPA's review of institutions responsible for the declaration of PAs in 2010, identified the following: National Parks Authority (National Parks Act, 1984); Forestry Unit under the Ministry of Agriculture (Forestry Act, revised 1989); Parks Commission under the Ministry of Lands (Public Parks Act, 1965); Fisheries Division under the Ministry of Agriculture (Marine Areas [Preservation and Enhancement] Act, 1974 and the Fisheries Act, revised 1989); Development Control Authority (Physical Planning Act 2003). No PAs have so far been declared under the Development Control Authority. Other agencies have since taken on lead roles in biodiversity conservation and protected areas management.

Department of Environment

The Department of Environment (DOE) under the Ministry of Health and the Environment has as its core mandate performance of functions for sustainable environmental protection and management in Antigua and Barbuda, including the implementation of various multilateral agreements on environment and climate change. Additionally, the DoE is responsible for oversight of the Sustainable Island Resource Framework Fund (SIRF Fund), which serves as the primary channel for environmental, climate mitigation and adaptation funding from international and domestic sources. The Department has been involved in awareness building and education, implementation of environmental projects/programmes, and the implementation of national obligations under several multilateral environmental agreements. Recently, under the Environmental Protection and Management Act, 2019 the DoE will be responsible for ensuring that the following management principles are applied:

1. Where the protected area is an ecotourism area, it shall be managed to: (a) protect and conserve the natural resources that offer an attraction to tourist visitors; and (b) regulate visitor activity to ensure that the carrying capacity of the natural resources is not exceeded.
2. Where the protected area is a foreshore reserve, it shall be managed in collaboration with the Fisheries Division to protect and conserve the marine resources within the reserve.
3. Where the protected area is a forest reserve, it shall be managed in collaboration with the Forestry and Agricultural Division to: (a) protect and preserve areas of natural forest; (b) ensure that the reserves natural processes continue unaffected by human activity; (c) protect its biological diversity to the greatest possible extent.
4. Where the protected area is a nature reserve, it shall be managed in a manner as to protect natural resources and maintain natural processes in an undisturbed state.
5. Where the protected area is a historical or cultural heritage site, or a marine reserve, or a national park, it shall be managed in collaboration with the National Parks Authority.
6. Where the protected area is a water catchment reserve, it shall be managed in a manner as to conserve, protect and manage the supply and quality of water available.
7. Where the protected area is a wetland, it shall be managed in a manner as to conserve the diversity and integrity of representative communities of wetland areas as specified the Convention on Wetlands of International Importance especially as Waterfowl Habitat; and
8. Where the area is protected as a carbon sink it shall be managed in accordance with internationally accepted principles.

National Parks Authority

The National Parks Authority (NPA) was established by legislation in 1984 as a not-for-profit, financially self-reliant statutory corporation overseeing spaces designated as National Parks under the 1984 Act. Currently the NPA manages the Nelson's Dockyard National Park and the Antigua Naval Dockyard and related archaeological sites - the UNESCO World Heritage Site, hosting over 130,000 visitors annually (pre-Covid19). It has in-house technical expertise and resources through its Environment Unit and Heritage Department to help manage the Nelson's Dockyard National Park, Green Castle National Park, Devil's Bridge National Park

and Fort Barrington National Park. Key activities include: public awareness, research, monitoring, management planning, enforcement of regulations and conservation of the natural and heritage resources in the parks. The Parks Commissioner and the Board of the National Parks Authority are also responsible for fund raising and financial management. There are also a number of tour guides, a Park Ranger and a Park Warden.

Forestry Unit – Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Barbuda Affairs

The Forestry Unit has been involved in awareness building and education for students and youth including topics such as: reforestation and conservation methods, climate change issues and mitigation techniques, trail blazing, biodiversity assessment, nursery, general plant care to include proper planting and pruning methods. The Unit has also undertaken reforestation and erosion control of the upper watershed at the Body Pond Conservation Area and has had technical inputs into all major activities involving terrestrial biodiversity. There is currently no documentation on the Unit's ability to manage all of the six Forest Reserves and six watersheds listed under Schedules IV and V of the EPMA, 2019.

Department of Agriculture - Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Barbuda Affairs

This department is responsible for regulatory, administration and technical services related to the development and management of farms and production-based agricultural enterprises. No documentation was available on this agency in the context of the management of Christian Valley lands under its jurisdiction.

Fisheries Division – Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Barbuda Affairs

This agency of government is responsible for, among other things, the declaration and management of marine reserves, management of the fishery and wetlands, research, monitoring, enforcement, education and awareness. The Division is a lead contributor to technical inputs on marine and wetland biodiversity conservation. No documentation was available to determine its current capacity to adequately manage marine PAs.

Parks Commission

This agency under the Ministry responsible for Lands, is accountable for the management of the public park - Long Bay Beach Park, created under the Public Parks Act, 1965. No information was available to determine their capacity to manage PAs. It should be noted that Pigeon Beach Park created under the Public Parks Act, 1965 is now managed by National Parks Authority.

Barbuda Council/ Barbuda National Parks Authority

The Barbuda Council through the Barbuda Land Act, 2007 was not included in the SPPA's review of institutions that could declare PAs. The Barbuda National Parks Authority was also established by legislation in 2014. The Barbuda Council has the responsibility for declaring and managing protected areas including marine reserves in and around the island of

Barbuda. No documentation was available to describe activities related to its capacity to manage PAs.

Environmental Awareness Group

The Environmental Awareness Group (EAG) was constituted as an organisation under the Friendly Societies Act in 1989. It is a key local non-governmental institution that has been involved in the conservation of biodiversity and PAs management over the past decades. The EAG has consistently demonstrated its ability for data collection, research, education and awareness building and project implementation especially in the context of invasive alien species, local flora and fauna, critically endangered plants and animals on offshore islands as well as other International Bird Areas and Key Biodiversity Areas. While the efforts of its members are often voluntary, it has undertaken consultancies and projects funded by other entities which documented its conservation work over the years.

Wallings Nature Reserve Inc.

Wallings Nature Reserve Inc. is a community-based, not-for-profit, non-governmental organisation that was registered in 2018 under the Companies Act, 1995. This NGO was established to manage the 680 ha Wallings Nature Reserve located in the hilly southwestern zone of the Shekerley Mountain Range. Since its inception in 2018, the Wallings Nature Reserve has received funding from 11 partners to help achieve the objectives of the organization, including the building of capacity of its members to better manage the Reserve.

Coordination

The SPPA noted that there were: “11 PAs representing six categories of PAs which fall under the responsibility of four separate agencies”. However, that list of declared PAs in AB did not include Forest Reserves as provided under the Forest Act. Under the Forestry Act: “Any land which at the date of the coming into force of this Act or at any time thereafter shall be in forest shall be deemed to be a forest reserve”. However, this Act did not specify what vegetation should be considered “in forest”. With the inclusion of the Barbuda Council, the DOE and the Forestry Unit, there are seven entities that have legislative responsibilities for managing different PAs.

The SPPA further noted those entities: “...that discharge responsibilities for the various facets of protected areas management derive their powers under separate legislative enactments or civil charters. In the absence of coordination these efforts result in a high level of duplication and inconsistent policy applications”.

In 2020, the Protected Areas Coordinating Mechanism (PACM) was initiated by the Department of Environment after a long process of discussions. The PACM is a committee comprised of all agencies responsible for protected area management in Antigua and Barbuda including representations of government agencies, non-governmental organizations, community groups and the private sector. The PACM will function as:

1. An advisory body to provide technical guidance on the development and implementation of the updated National Plan for a System of Protected Areas (NPSPA) in Antigua and Barbuda, and periodically review and update the NPSPA every 5 years. This NPSPA will ensure the effective administration and management of any area that is declared to be a protected area under the relevant laws in Antigua and Barbuda.
2. An advisory body to provide technical guidance on the management of the National Plan for a System of Protected Areas once the National Plan for a System of Protected Areas is approved by Cabinet.
3. An advisory group to provide guidance and recommendations on technical issues to new and existing protected areas pertinent to biodiversity conservation. This refers to any protected area declared under the relevant laws in Antigua and Barbuda.
4. An oversight committee for monitoring the development and implementation of protected area management plans in matters related to biodiversity conservation for new protected areas and any that request assistance.
5. A clearinghouse mechanism to share data and information in matters related to biodiversity conservation to ensure all protected area managers have access to information needed for their work on biodiversity. The Department of Environment will be responsible for storing this data and information in the national Environmental Information Management and Advisory System (EIMAS). According to the EPMA 2019, the EIMAS shall be responsible for storing information concerning the natural resources of Antigua and Barbuda. The data and information are available to the protected area managers and/or the public by means of the online Natural Resources Inventory.
6. A collaborative body that can facilitate knowledge sharing and networking on effective protected area management among local protected area authorities/ stakeholders and regional scientific community agencies in respect to biodiversity and ecosystem related matters.
7. A resource of technical expertise for conducting biodiversity monitoring in protected areas. The technical expertise can be provided by members of the PACM.

Financing

The major mechanism for financing elements of PA management has been funds from external donors for national or regional projects. Some government generated funding through annual budgetary allocations has been available, largely for salaries and incidentals for existing staff of government agencies. However, the NPA is wholly self-financing, covering its expense with revenues raised through park management and grant and donor funding solicited for specific projects related to its operations. The current Path to 2020

Project is an example of an external donor financed (Global Environmental Facility – GEF) biodiversity conservation project. This project aims to: actualize protection and sustainable use of biodiversity and protected areas, under the umbrella of the newly passed Environmental Protection and Management Act. The GEF project grant is about US\$2.7 million, executed by the DOE and implemented by the UNEP.

The SIRF Fund, administered by the DoE is a new mechanism that is expected to address the problem of adequate, sustainable financing for projects related to environmental management and the implementation of multilateral environmental agreements to which Antigua and Barbuda are party. Within the SIRF Fund there are different Thematic Funding Windows in which funds for specific purposes can be set aside and administered separately from the general funds. Income to the SIRF Fund is provided through domestic and international sources. Domestic sources include Green Card park visitation fees, pollution charges, carbon credits, taxes, levies, and other fees as may be prescribed by regulation (not yet implemented).

Requests for financing the annual operational programmes of government departments and ministries must be submitted to the Ministry of Finance and Corporate Governance for approval. A Prioritization Framework was described in the Medium Term Development Strategy, 2016-2020 (MTDS). This can be used by government departments for assessing Base Expenditure Allocations in cases of significant resource scarcity.

The MTDS Prioritization Framework considers four critical aspects of policy implementation:

1. **Level of Urgency:** The degree to which an action is required in order to avoid near-term, system-critical disruptions or missed opportunities. Actions deemed urgent receive higher priority.
2. **Level of Impact:** The degree to which an action leads to visible and measurable improvements in quality of life for Antiguan and Barbudans in the Medium-Term. High-impact actions receive higher priority.
3. **Availability of Resources:** The extent to which resources (either internally generated or external) have already been or can be easily committed to the action. “Resources” include financial as well as human resources necessary to implement the policy. Actions linked to existing or easily mobilized resources receive higher priority.
4. **Net Systemic Contribution:** The extent to which an action contributes, over time, to the integrated or systemic achievement of the Sustainable Development Dimensions (SDD). This criterion involves assessing whether the action contributes to multiple SDDs, or whether its implementation comes at a cost (trade-off) to other SDDs. Actions that contribute more highly to multiple SDDs, without trade-offs, receive higher priority. Actions and initiatives designed to be cross-cutting should score highly on this criterion, by design.

In the context of resource constraints faced by all government agencies, the framework should be used to inform programme design when requesting annual allocations to support the operations of PAs in the country.

Business and Sustainable Financing Plan

The recent “A Business and Sustainable Financing Plan for Antigua and Barbuda’s System of Protected Areas 2021-2031” completed under the The Path to 2020 Project, provides a detailed implementation plan and costing for the financial strategies that are intended for protecting the natural, cultural and historic values of the country’s protected areas. The financing plan estimated that the annual costs for managing the existing system of protected areas will be approximately US\$3 million (XC\$8.1 million) per annum with a further US\$3.5 million required to get the PA’s up and running over the next 3 - 5 years as outlined in their draft management plans. National financing strategies proposed to meet those projected costs include: PA levies on tourism; green card initiative; offsetting flights; and cost saving strategies. Four main disbursement mechanisms also were identified for the SIRF: submission of annual PA budgets based on the management plan to the Thematic Board; issuing grants; providing microfinancing loans and equity. A five-year road map, with costings and Key Performance Indicators (KPI’s), was provided for the implementation of the financing plan.

Status of Protected Areas in Antigua and Barbuda

Currently there are twelve declared and six proposed PAs in Antigua and Barbuda. Table 1 provides the status of those sites, the managing entities, the staffing and current activities of the assigned staff.

Table 1. Status of protected areas in Antigua and Barbuda showing staffing and activities. Courtesy: Dept. of Environment, May 2021 with further input from the National Parks Authority and the Environmental Awareness Group, June 2021.

Name of PA	Management Authority	Main Person Managing Area (Officers etc.)	No. of staff	Activities
Declared Protected Areas				
Cades Bay Marine Reserve	Fisheries Division	Tricia Lovell (Deputy Chief Fisheries Officer) Mr. Mark Archibald (Fisheries Officer)	8 technical staff (no manager of any MPAs)	Monitoring of reef systems in collaboration with coast guard, enforcement of legislation.
Est. 1999				
Diamond Reef and Salt Fish Tail Reef				
Est. 1973				EAG monitors terrestrial keystone species (e.g. Antiguan Racer) and implement management mechanisms for species habitat.
Northeast Marine Management Area (NEMMA)	Fisheries Division (offshore islands monitoring done by EAG – not mandated)	FISHERIES Tricia Lovell (Deputy Chief Fisheries officer) Mr. Mark Archibald (Fisheries Officer)		
Est. 2005				

Name of PA	Management Authority	Main Person Managing Area (Officers etc.)	No. of staff	Activities
		EAG Arica Hill (EAG Executive Director) Shanna Challenger (EAG Offshore Islands Programme Coordinator) Britney Hay (Wildlife Officer) Johnella Bradshaw (Redonda Ecosystems Reserve Coordinator) Nathan Wilson (Invasive Species Officer) Kariana Kelsick (Programme Assistant)		
Goat Point Sanctuary Est. 2014	Barbuda Fisheries	Roy Morris (Fisheries Officer)	4 (3 fisheries officers and 1 cadet)	Small patrols in the area to make sure there are no fishing activities happening in the area.
Low Bay Sanctuary Est. 2014				
Palaster Reef Sanctuary Est. 1973				
Two Foot Bay Sanctuary Est. 2014				
Codrington Lagoon Est. 2005	Barbuda Council	Kelly Burton (CLNP Manager)	2 (Manager and 1 other person)	Monitoring and patrolling
Devil's Bridge Est. 2007	National Parks Authority	<i>Overall Manager</i> Ann Marie Martin (Parks Commissioner)	5 The staff compliment of	Monitoring, Evaluations, Assessments, Draft/execute
Fort Barrington				

Name of PA	Management Authority	Main Person Managing Area (Officers etc.)	No. of staff	Activities
Est. 2008 Greencastle Hill		<i>Environment Unit</i> Ruleta Camacho Thomas (Coordinator) Ruleo Camacho (Marine Ecologist) Shantice White (Trainee) <i>Heritage Department</i> Desley Gardner (Heritage Resources Officer) Christopher Waters (Director)	the NPA fluctuates from 90-70 persons_ (pre covid). Since COVID the staff number has hovered at around 70 persons. While 5 are directly employed by the Heritage and Environment Units, other staff of the NPA support the overall management of the Parks under the management of the NPA.	policy, special projects, strategic planning.
Est. 2007				
Nelson's Dockyard National Park (Actively)				
Est. 1984				
Proposed Protected Areas				
Boggy Peak National Park	Public- Private Partnership	Boggy Peak/SMMA Management Authority	5-prospective	Monitor and enforce regulations; protect park resources and values; provide for visitor enjoyment; and address mutual interests in the quality of life of community members.
Wallings Reservoir	Forestry Unit	Adriel Thibou (Senior Forestry Officer)	(no staff – presently drafting MOU)	-
Wallings Nature Reserve	Wallings Nature Reserve Inc.	Refica Attwood (Executive Director) + team	2 (full time) 15+ (volunteers)	Monitoring, patrolling and enforcing (to an extent)
Redonda Ecosystem	EAG	Johnella Bradshaw (Redonda	6 (including coordinator)	Implement interim

Name of PA	Management Authority	Main Person Managing Area (Officers etc.)	No. of staff	Activities
Reserve		Ecosystems Reserve Coordinator)		management plan.
Christian Valley	Min. of Agriculture	Petranilla Joseph + other Extension Officers, Managers of the Agriculture Stations	3 (district officer + regulatory officers)	Education and training (district officer) Land allocation issues and education/ training (regulatory officer)
Shekerley Mountain Management Area (SMMA)	Public- Private Partnership	SMMA Management Authority	6 (SMMA Co-ordinator (1) Tourism Product Development and Communication Specialist (1) Environment Specialist (1) Admin Officer (1) Logistics and Maintenance Officer (1) Rangers (2)	Implementation of the management plan monitoring and enforcement conducting and overseeing all on-ground monitoring and compliance activities

The spatial locations of these protected areas are provided in Figures 1, 2 and 3

Appendix 2 provides a summary of the location and key features of the protected areas listed in Table 1.

Note: The Environmental Protection and Management Act, 2019 in Schedule IV lists several sites as Forest Reserves and Protected Watersheds. However, these sites have no defined boundaries as yet. The establishment of a Watersheds and Wetlands Management Committee is proposed for the management of those sites, but it is not yet constituted. There is currently no active management of these watersheds.

Figure 1: Map of the protected and ecologically sensitive areas in Antigua, including marine protected areas, proposed and established National Parks and Key Biodiversity Areas.

Created by Janel Johnston at the Department of Environment for DCA, to show National Parks, Protected Areas, and Environmentally Sensitive Sites in Antigua. Data sourced from the Environmental Information Management and Advisory System, January 2020. Basemap: Esri Light Grey Canvas.

Figure 2: Map of approximate extent of the proposed Shekerley Mountain Management Area, proximity to local communities, and the proposed boundaries of Boggy Peak National Park, Greencastle Hill National Park, Wallings Nature Reserve, and the Christian Valley Conservation Area.

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Figure 3: Map of the protected and ecologically sensitive areas in Barbuda, including marine protected areas, proposed and established National Parks and Key Biodiversity Areas.

Created by Janeil Johnston at the Department of Environment to show National Parks and Protected Areas in Barbuda.
 Data sourced from the Environmental Information Management and Advisory System, February 2020.
 Basemap: Esri Light Grey Canvas.

<*> Appendix ... Summary of PAs key features.

Establishment of Protected Areas

The procedure for the establishment of protected areas is defined in law under the EPMA, 2019. Section 55 states that the Minister may, by order, designate any area of land or any area within the territorial seas of Antigua and Barbuda as a protected area in order to:

- (a) safeguard and maintain representative samples of the natural ecosystems and endangered species that occur in those ecosystems;
- (b) propagate, protect, conserve, study and manage any ecosystem, flora, fauna or landscape;
- (c) protect examples of natural or scientific interest including fossilized wood and Forest of Stones;
- (d) provide educational and recreational areas that will permit the public to obtain valuable information on the resources of the protected area and appreciate and enjoy the values of protected areas;
- (e) provide for multiple-use resource areas which offer protection to ecosystems and resources while providing secondary social and economic benefit; or
- (f) in the case of areas declared as forest reserves, as a carbon sink, adaptation measure and for the conservation of soil and water.

Section 56 of the Act prescribes the procedure for designating Crown lands as protected areas and Section 57 provides for the designation of private lands as protected areas. This Act is likely to become one of the main instruments for the designation or declaration of new protected areas in the country.

Further guidance on the selection of sites for protection is contained in the National Standards and Key Performance Indicators for Antigua and Barbuda's Protected Areas recently developed by a consultant in 2020 for the Department of Environment. This document indicated that the IUCN Green List Standards were used as a key reference and is based the four main components for PA success: good governance, sound design and planning, effective management and conservation outcomes.

Management Instruments

Written management plans exist for at least 9 sites in the country: Nelson's Dockyard National Park (1985), North East Marine Management Area (2007), Wallings Forest Conservation Area (2009), Body Ponds Watershed Management Area (2009), Codrington Lagoon National Park (2009), Cades Bay Marine Reserve (2012), Boggy Peak National Park (2020), Draft Management Plan for the Redonda Ecosystem Reserve (2020) and the Shekerley Mountains Management Area (2021).

All of these plans provide information on the context and purpose for protection, the resources at the site, threats or issues related to the site, the objectives for management, key management activities, a proposed management framework and an indication of sources of financing. Any management plan older than six years should be revised or updated as needed.

The key challenges in all of these plans, as is common elsewhere in the Caribbean, is the recruitment of an adequate number of quality staff and the timely financing for staffing, equipment, infrastructure and operational activities. These will need to be addressed for the full implementation of the National Plan for the System of Protected Areas.

PA management plans will be effective if the challenges identified above are addressed, but there must also be an alignment with the perceived values of the protected area and its management objectives. Table 2 provides a summary of the values of some protected areas that were identified by the agencies that had jurisdiction over or responsibility for aspects of management of these sites. The input from these agencies were in response to a questionnaire completed during March 2021 and was based on: METT-4 A guide to the online Excel version of the Management Effectiveness Tracking Tool (METT) for protected and conserved areas (Stolton, S., Hockings, M and N. Dudley. 2020).

Table 2. Values of some protected areas (declared and proposed) identified by key agencies in Antigua and Barbuda.

Protected Area Values	Barbuda Council [Codrington Lagoon National Park]	Forestry Unit [Body Pond Watershed]	Wallings Nature Reserve Inc. [Wallings Nature Reserve]	National Parks Authority [Nelson’s Dockyard National Park]	Environmental Awareness Group [Redonda Ecosystem Reserve]
Natural Values					
Major natural values should include nature or biodiversity values (e.g. threatened species, priority habitats or ecosystems)	√	Major water shed, critical bat habitat, threatened plant species habitat	√	√	√
Ecological processes	√	√		√	√
Landscape and connectivity values	√	Critical vegetation cover from ridge to reef	√	√	Ridge to reef
Geological and geomorphological features	√	√		√	Collapsed volcanic dome
Paleontological values	√	√		√	Shell middens
Scenic values and outstanding natural beauty	√	Spectacular natural vista from highest point	√	√	√

Protected Area Values	Barbuda Council [Codrington Lagoon National Park]	Forestry Unit [Body Pond Watershed]	Wallings Nature Reserve Inc. [Wallings Nature Reserve]	National Parks Authority [Nelson's Dockyard National Park]	Environmental Awareness Group [Redonda Ecosystem Reserve]
Social Values					
Recreational use	√	Hiking, camping, bird watching, star gazing, freshwater fishing, off-roading	√	√	Limited hiking, fishing and diving
Social significance to local, regional or national communities	√	Largest watershed on the island; demonstration site for a major regional project	√	√	√
Historic sites and structures	√	Victoria architecture, historically significant source of water for the island	√	√	Relics from industrial mining era
Cultural Values					
Significance to indigenous/local people	√		√	√	
Sites and artefacts of indigenous/ local importance	√		√	√	Shell middens
Sites with importance to faith groups and religions				√	
Historical or archaeological importance		√	√	√	√
Access to resources of cultural importance (e.g. medicinal plants and traditionally harvested resources)	√	√	√	√	

Protected Area Values	Barbuda Council [Codrington Lagoon National Park]	Forestry Unit [Body Pond Watershed]	Wallings Nature Reserve Inc. [Wallings Nature Reserve]	National Parks Authority [Nelson's Dockyard National Park]	Environmental Awareness Group [Redonda Ecosystem Reserve]
Economic Values					
Tourism or recreational use of the area	✓	Several tour operators conduct tours in the area recreational activities mentioned above	✓	✓	Few guided tours
Sustainable use of resources	✓	Still being developed	✓	✓	Fishing
Payments for ecosystem services		Some services	✓	✓	

All of the selected PAs have multiple values which suggest that these sites should have management objectives that are consistent with those values identified by the agency responsible for these sites. Table 3 identifies the management objectives of the most recent PA management plan as an example: the Shekerley Mountains Management Area (SMMA) and the corresponding PA values. The SMMA includes, among other areas, the Boggy Peak National Park, much of Greencastle Hill National Park, Christian Valley and Wallings Forest Reserve. This example shows that a recently prepared PA management plan has objectives that are aligned with the values identified by PA managers.

Table 3. Management objectives of the Shekerley Mountains Management Area and corresponding protected area values.

SMMA Management Objectives	Associated Protected Area Values
<u>Programme 1: Land Management and Use</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To ensure appropriate management structures are developed and implemented together with communities and key stakeholders • To develop and implement an effective land use management plan with clearly defined zones, regulations and guidelines for allowed activities • To control the impacts and spread of Invasive species • To develop and implement a comprehensive pollution and sustainable waste management programme 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Natural Value

<p><u>Programme 2: Monitoring and Compliance</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To establish and implement an effective monitoring programme that includes monitoring biological and ecological indicators • To establish and implement an effective compliance programme with appropriate regulations and guidelines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Natural Value ○ Economic Value
<p><u>Programme 3: Knowledge and Appreciation</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To increase knowledge and understanding of SMMA's natural and cultural values and history • To increase appreciation and pride in Antiguans and Barbudans of SMMA's natural and cultural values and history 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Natural Value ○ Cultural Value
<p><u>Programme 4: Sustainable Livelihoods and Recreation</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To develop and strengthen Eco-tourism and Heritage/Cultural Tourism opportunities in and around the SMMA • To increase opportunities for non-tourism related livelihoods that are financially sustainable and in harmony with nature • To enhance the natural space encouraging people to use it for enjoyment towards a healthy lifestyle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Economic Value ○ Social Value ○ Natural Value

The objectives of the SMMA are clearly intended to address some aspects of the values for which the site will be protected. Congruency between PA values and management objectives are necessary first steps towards ensuring that PA sites can be managed effectively. Since most of the PA sites in the country were legally designated between 1973 and 2005, which suggests that some kind of management activities would likely have taken place, at some time, based on the availability of human and financial resources. An assessment of the management effectiveness of protected areas will therefore give a good indication of existing capacities and gaps that will require attention.

Management Effectiveness

The Management Effectiveness Tracking Tool (METT) developed by the World Wildlife Fund (WWF) and its partners is perhaps the most common protected areas management effectiveness tool, used in over 2,500 protected areas in at least 127 countries. The current version METT-4 now comes in an EXCEL spreadsheet for ease of data entry and analysis. It is designed with a range of key questions covering many elements that contribute to management effectiveness of a protected area and can be administered by anyone. Staff of all PA agencies in AB were given an online orientation in February 2021 on how to complete the METT-4 for PAs under their jurisdiction. These agencies were then asked to complete the METT-4 spreadsheet during February to May 2012 and submit to the DoE for use in preparing this National Plan for the System Protected Areas. Table 4 summarises the

responses from four agencies which identified the actions to improve the effectiveness of their management of key PA sites.

Table 4. Summary of the elements in the METT-4 and responses from PA entities on actions to improve their management effectiveness. Where the value in a cell is '0', this indicates that no information was provided by the respondent or that the response was not consistent with or related to the management component.

Management Component METT-4	Actions To Improve Management Effectiveness			
	Forestry Unit	CLNP	Wallings NR	NDNP
1. Legal status	Seeking protection of upper watershed as a forest reserve.	Yes, 2005	Not yet declared.	National Parks Act 1984.
2. Management based on protected area objectives	0	More staff, funding and support needed for management.	Develop/update management plan.	Development of strategic natural resources management plan.
3. Protected area regulations/controls	New Forestry Act is being drafted; amendments to current Forest Act being done in meantime.	Stronger MoU between agencies and collaboration between PA agencies and the government.	Management team unable to address regulations/control... government has responsibility.	Amendments to regulations, guidelines and processes for development to be done.
4. Contribution to achievement of management objectives by adjacent land/sea use	0	No influence of the PA management body on areas outside of the PA.	Manager will work with SMMA management agency to achieve sound land use management outside of the Reserve.	Land use planning inside the PA needed.
5. Adequacy of protected area design	0	0	Through research the area can be adjusted to ensure that the values are being protected over time. The boundaries should be reassessed to ensure that the main values/resources are included within the PA.	Zoning and special use areas need to be identified and approved, where allowed activities are described.
6. Protected area boundary demarcation	0	The community needs to be better engaged through a new public awareness strategy.	Management agency can recommend actions or changes to the boundaries.	Need to improve public awareness.
7. Management plan implementation	0	The plan is being revised with special focus on implementation	The management agency can work towards developing a formal	Management plan needs updating/revision to include strategic natural

Management Component METT-4	Actions To Improve Management Effectiveness			
		with available resources.	management plan/agreement.	resource management and visitor management plan.
8. Regular work plan implementation	To improve workplan, a management plan is needed as well as financing and legislation.	More funding as well as a budget is needed for management activities.	Update workplan as needed.	0
9. Information for management	Human capacity needed to implement activities related to biodiversity, research and monitoring.	More studies and a new monitoring plan needed based on available resources.	Training on skills needed to manage these resources, including monitoring and surveying to identify gaps.	Strategic natural resource management plan needed.
10. Staffing adequacy	Co-management being considered to improve capacity	A budget to hire and keep new staff needed.	If enough funding is secured then additional staff can be hired.	Recruitment and training of more staff needed.
11. Adequacy of knowledge and skills	Hiring a soil and water engineer.	More training of staff needed.	Training for staff needed.	Training of staff on environmental management needed.
12. Adequacy of budget	Budget increase requested for area that contributes to food security e.g. Body Ponds.	A budget is needed.	Work on finding more funding to support budget	Need to raise grant money and attract donors.
13. Security of budget	0	A budget is needed and funds secured.	More funding needed.	Need to find ways to reduce recurrent expenses (energy, water, insurance); explore new sources of revenue (diving, etc.); increase the attractiveness of the PA to donors.
14. Effectiveness of budget management	0	0	0	Explore sustainable financing opportunities for environmental management.
15. Adequacy of equipment and facilities	Additional equipment and training in use of equipment needed.	0	Funds needed for purchasing more equipment.	Need a boat and drone.
16. Law enforcement capability	Stronger legislation or amendment to existing Act needed.	Fines need to be implemented and laws enforced.	0	Enhance collaboration with police; signage and notification of laws; enhance NPA enforcement capacity.
17. Control of	0	MoU needed	0	Enforcement capacity

Management Component METT-4	Actions To Improve Management Effectiveness			
access/resource use		between the NPA and the Barbuda Council		needs enhancement with regulations and equipment; more public support and buy-in for the PA.
18. Staff safety	Additional safety and firefighting equipment needed.	0	Ongoing safety training to staff.	0
19. Management oriented surveys and research	Increased expertise needed for various tasks.	Expertise needed.	Nothing to improve at this time.	Strategic natural resource management plan needed.
20. Monitoring and evaluation	More formalised system of recording data could be employed.	Training needed for these activities.	The M&E document will be used to monitor activities and keep them on track.	0
21. Resource management operations	Stronger relationship with the Fire Dept needed.	Stronger policy needed.	Clearing of paths to reduce fires, removal of invasive species where possible. More education on the PA values.	Marine turtle fencing with buoys; signage with fisheries regulations; developing educational materials for fisher folks; education material for yachting people.
22. Climate change adaptation	Full implementation of the SIRMM recommendations for the Forestry Unit and Body Ponds area.	Awareness only.	Management needs technical assistance to develop an adaptation plan.	0
23. Carbon loss prevention and carbon capture	Promotion of the initiative in hotels, better transportation equipment for guests, improvements to the GIS Unit for guests to better track the tree growth and health from home.	0	No action at this time.	0
24. Ecosystem services provision	Fully implement the recommended activities of the SIRMM and fully established water resources, watershed and wetlands management	Expertise and technical training needed.	0	0

Management Component METT-4	Actions To Improve Management Effectiveness			
	committee.			
25. Education programmes linked to management needs	Completion of management plan to include a public awareness programme	Implementation plan needed.	Design awareness campaigns to target all audiences.	Improvement needed in education and communication activities e.g. newsletter; education programme on coastal and marine environment for schools; exhibit on marine resources present in the PA to be put in museum; materials on the PA for visitors.
26. Cooperation with neighbours and commercial entities	0	0	0	Continue current relationship.
27. Commercial tourism operators contribution	0	0	0	Education, awareness of taxi drivers, fisher folks, yachties, etc. Enforcement of regulations of taxi drivers. Feedback from commercial tourism people.
28. Fees	0	MoU needed with the Barbuda Council.	Ongoing training to better manage fees.	0
29. Adequacy of visitor facilities and services	Trails need improvements to meet international standards.	0	Bathroom facilities could be improved.	Need proper understanding of visitors, especially at the Georgian Museum.
30. Local communities involvement	0	0	Persons call or send inputs.	Continue consultation with local communities.
31. Livelihood benefits	0	0	Current system is working	0
32. Threats mitigation	Better equipment and training in fire suppression needed. More public announcements for fire prevention needed.	Through cooperation with developers, the government and the PA.	Current system is working	0
33. Connectivity assessed and implemented	0	0	0	0
34. Condition of	0	Sand mining needs	Some action based	0

Management Component METT-4 natural values	Actions To Improve Management Effectiveness			
		to stop.	on expert guidance.	
35. Condition of cultural values	0	0	Repairs to be done to the reservoir.	0
36. Conservation status of key indicator species	Propagation and reforestation programme for <i>Sterculia sp.</i>	0	0	0
37. Conservation status of habitats	0	0	0	0

The capacity related actions identified by the PA agencies that were able to complete and send in their METT-4 assessments are summarized below, also in the context of the data from Table 1. It should be noted that the NPA (NDNP) provided information on their 2018 METT assessment which had a slightly different structure and less components than the more recent METT-4 template.

1. Staffing: All agencies indicated the need for more human resources, even the NPA which had the highest number of personnel assigned to PA management. Some agencies seemed to be greatly under-staffed.
2. Training: All agencies confirmed the need for training or more training of staff.
3. Budget: All agencies needed more funding to support PA operations including equipment and infrastructure. Some PAs seemed to be grossly underfunded.

Effective management of PAs cannot be realized if the three core capacity elements summarized above are not addressed in a timely manner. Also, the main roles and responsibilities of PA agencies must be understood, accepted and discharged efficiently to ensure management effectiveness.

Roles and Responsibilities in Managing Protected Areas

A guideline for the preparation of PA management plans was prepared for the Department of Environment in January 2021 (Appendix 2). Online training on the use of this guideline was provided to staff of the PA management entities in March 2021. This guideline outlined a range of key activities that ought to be considered in the management of any protected area. These key activities were therefore the basis of deciding on the required roles and responsibilities for any PA management entity.

A summary of the required roles and responsibilities were used in a one-page questionnaire that was sent to all protected area agencies in February 2021. PA agencies were asked to identify what they considered relevant in relation to the protected areas under its care. The

following list summarises the major PA management activities that were agreed by the entities/agencies that responded to the questionnaire.

Planning, Management and Administration

- PA policy and implementation
- Project planning and management
- Organisational leadership
- Human resources management
- Financial resources management
- Procurement
- Administrative documentation and reporting
- Communication and collaboration

Applied Protected Area Management

- Managing visitor use (also interpretation and tour guiding)
- Surveillance and enforcement of laws/regulations
- Monitoring and research (including impacts, visitor use, policy/ management prescriptions, etc.)
- Installation of infrastructure or equipment (e.g. signage, trails, visitor use facilities, etc.)
- Maintenance of site (including habitats and historic sites) or equipment
- Site restoration /rehabilitation
- Awareness building and education
- Engaging adjacent communities including managing conflicts

All of the PA entities/agencies had varying capacities for implementation of each of the PA management activities identified above. In a few cases, an agency did not consider that it had the ability or authority to undertake some of the activities. For example the NGOs indicated that the enforcement of legislation/regulations was under the jurisdiction of law enforcement officers and officers of the respective government agencies, such as the Fisheries Division. NGOs also felt that the government has responsibility for protected areas policy and for oversight of its implementation. Where staffing and funds were the limiting factors, many of the activities identified above were not carried out for many of the PA sites in the country.

Training Needs for PA Management

A survey of the training needs of PA entity/agencies in relation to the roles and responsibilities in managing PAs was conducted via a questionnaire during March to May 2021. Table 5 provides a summary of the training needs identified by those agencies that responded to the questionnaire.

Table 5. Training needs responses by PA managing entities in Antigua and Barbuda.

Role and Responsibility	Codrington Lagoon National Park (Barbuda Council)	Forestry Unit	Wallings Nature Reserve Inc.	National Parks Authority	Environmental Awareness Group
Training Needs in Planning, Management and Administration					
PA policy and implementation			Additional training required		
Project planning and management		Project management for junior staff		Ecosystem management and engineering; risk management; resilience; climate change	Management methods specific to PAs
Organisational leadership	Training needed				
Human resources management	Staff needed				
Financial resources management			Additional training required		Sustainable financing mechanisms
Procurement					Developing ToRs specific to PA staff e.g. tour guides and wardens
Administrative documentation and reporting					
Communication and collaboration					
Training Needs in Applied Protected Area Management					
Managing visitor use (also interpretation and tour guiding)					Training in tour guiding; customer service; marketing and promotion
Surveillance and enforcement of laws			Additional training required		Surveillance methods
Monitoring and research (including	Training needed	Biodiversity monitoring and research	Additional training required	Understanding ecosystem functionality	Visitor use impacts; carrying

Role and Responsibility	Codrington Lagoon National Park (Barbuda Council)	Forestry Unit	Wallings Nature Reserve Inc.	National Parks Authority	Environmental Awareness Group
impacts, visitor use, policy/management prescriptions, etc.)		including: entomology; GIS; soil science		and basic ecosystem assessment including: geology and hydrology; terrestrial ecology; plant diseases identification and management; forestry management; soil rehabilitation; applied climate change; adaptive management for agriculture; ecosystem valuation	capacity; plant and invertebrate identification and analysis; reintroduction of species; tracking of seabirds; deep sea monitoring methods
Installation of infrastructure or equipment (e.g. signage, trails, visitor use facilities, etc.)			Additional training required		Permanent weather/climate station; visitor use facilities; trail maintenance
Maintenance of site (including habitats and historic sites) or equipment		Small engine repairs			Invasive plant management; maintenance of historic relics; water quality monitoring
Site restoration /rehabilitation					Coral restoration
Awareness building and education		Web design/programming		Adaptability to social media; professionally trained staff	
Engaging adjacent communities including managing conflicts			Additional training required	User group conflict management e.g. yachting and fishermen; understanding the value of real estate	Engagement with neighbouring countries who use the Redonda area; conflict resolution

Some agencies seem not to need any training in particular areas which may suggest that they either already have such skills, or have no capacity to undertake the required responsibilities. Monitoring and research were the only role/responsibility where all agencies indicated the need for training. A Participatory Monitoring Method for Protected Areas in Antigua and Barbuda was developed in February 2021 and an online orientation session on this methodology was conducted with staff from several agencies with activities in or responsibility for protected areas (Appendix 3).

The responses suggested that the NGOs required skills that may reside with some of the government agencies which presents an opportunity for closer collaboration and mutual training. Care must be taken to ensure that training for staff is specific (including refresher courses) and addresses existing priority needs, that when met, can be applied immediately. It has been common in the Caribbean over the past two decades that personnel attend a range of sponsored training courses and very little improvement is seen or sustained in the working environment thereafter.

Implementation Plan for Managing the System of Protected Areas

Tourism has been the major contributor to the economy of AB. Both marine and terrestrial ecosystems serve as key areas for local natural resource users (e.g. fisher folk) as well as for local and foreign visitors seeking either passive or active recreation. Many, if not all of the PA sites, either legally designated or proposed, meet the recreational needs of visitors and provide livelihood opportunities or ecosystem services for citizens. However, the quality of the visitor experience and quantity, diversity and health of the associated biodiversity are very much dependent of the management of the PA sites.

This section focuses on building capacity to enable improved management for the system of protected areas in key components that emerged from the responses of PA entities and review of the literature.

Quality Assurance

The Protected Areas Coordinating Mechanism and the PA managers should have overall responsibility for quality control/assurance of PA management activities but may call upon specific technical expertise to assist as needed. Continuous improvement in the performance of PA staff should be encouraged, especially through periodic examination in detail of how work is currently carried out, and challenging every aspect of it; whether it needs doing at all, and whether it is done in the right way, at the right time and by the right people.

The adoption of a quality management system is a strategic decision for an organization that can help to improve its overall performance, its ability to consistently provide products and services that meet customer and applicable statutory and regulatory requirements; and to enhance customer satisfaction. In deciding on the quality management system perhaps the first questions that the PA manager has to ask are: "Whom do we serve?" and "Whom should we serve?" The system of PAs should be serving at least, the needs of the majority of users of the PAs, while ensuring that the natural resources and ecosystem services are not adversely impacted and the quality of the visitor experience is not diminished. So, the product will be healthy marine and terrestrial habitats and abundant, diverse species and the service with the activities (processes) undertaken to keep these resources healthy and abundant.

Elements of the International Standard ISO 9001 Quality Management System

-Requirements (ISO, 2015), should be considered in guiding the quality assurance of the PAs operations, especially in the application of the seven quality management principles of this Standard:

1. Customer focus
2. Leadership
3. Engagement of people
4. Process approach
5. Improvement
6. Evidence-based decision making, and
7. Relationship management.

One of the key elements of the ISO 9001 standard, relevant to the system of PAs, is that the organization should determine the processes (activities) needed for the quality management system and should:

- i. determine the inputs required and the outputs expected from these processes;
- ii. determine the sequence and interaction of these processes;
- iii. determine and apply the criteria and methods (including monitoring, measurements and related performance indicators) needed to ensure the effective operation and control of these processes;
- iv. determine the resources needed for these processes and ensure their availability;
- v. assign the responsibilities and authorities for these processes;
- vi. address the risks and opportunities as determined in accordance with requirements;
- vii. evaluate these processes and implement any changes needed to ensure that these processes achieve their intended results;
- viii. improve the processes and the quality management system;
- ix. maintain documented information to support the operation of its processes;
- x. retain documented information to have confidence that the processes are being carried out as planned.

Other elements of the ISO 9001 standard that will be of use to the Protected Areas Coordinating Mechanism and the PA managers are: the Guidance on Support (resources, competence, awareness and communication), Operational Planning and Control, and Performance Evaluation.

Staffing

The Protected Areas Coordinating Mechanism and the PA managers will need to undertake a human resources needs assessment for the effective management of the entire system of protected areas. The 16 roles and responsibilities identified in the first column of Table 5 should be considered in identifying the types of personnel, numbers of personnel and the levels at which they are needed to operate. For example, senior rangers, junior rangers, biologists, communication officers, etc. Once the assessment is completed and the numbers

and type of personnel are agreed, the job specifications could then be prepared and the process of recruitment initiated. It should also be decided how personnel will be allocated among the PA sites or rotated among sites, or serve for specific periods at specific sites depending on the priority needs of each site. The priority needs of each PA site should also be determined.

Training

There are several opportunities that are potentially available to address many of the skills training needs that were identified by respondents. Firstly, consideration should be given to a “Training Exchange”, engaging PA agencies or other local agencies with the requisite expertise to provide training to the entities that need those skills. For example, the Forestry Unit may be able to train the National Parks Authority in forestry management and the Agricultural Extension Dept. may be able to train the National Parks Authority in plant diseases identification and management. Alternately, there could be collaboration MOUs established so that Government agencies can provide services to PA managers where it is not practical for the specialization to be developed for each park. For example, the Plant Protection Division and Forestry Unit can potentially, carry out periodic surveys in the Nelson’s Dockyard National Park to identify plant diseases, assess risk and design action plans to address threats. Similarly, the Environmental Awareness Group may be able to provide the Forestry Unit with training on biodiversity monitoring and the Wallings Nature Reserve Inc., could provide the Forestry Unit with project management training. So, discussion and negotiation among the PA agencies should be held to determine whom can provide each other with training on specific topics.

The second approach to address the training, is the use of free online and paid courses via the internet. There are several good sites that offer verified online training. It is recommended that, **edX** (<https://www.edx.org>) and **Coursera** (<https://www.coursera.org>) be seriously considered as avenues for individuals who are willing to upgrade their skills. The focus of training could be on skills that are not otherwise available or accessible or that may be required for the unique management priorities for a specific area.

The third approach to consider, is the development of a comprehensive training agenda for PA staff with an identification of priority topics. This should be done via joint meetings with all PAs entities in collaboration with the Dept. of Environment. Then agencies should agree on a mechanism for implementation of the required training and seek grant funding from the SIF Fund or through the Organisation of Eastern Caribbean States to undertake the training. This training agenda should include ‘learning by doing’, supervised practical hands-on work of fixed duration as well as opportunities for short attachments to other PAs in the OECS and wider Caribbean that can provide the required learning.

Several Caribbean training resources that would be useful in preparation of the training agenda are:

1. Level 2 – Maintenance of Parks and Protected Terrestrial Areas (CANTA/CARICOM) available under ‘Agriculture Industry’ at

<http://www.ntarestore.org/nta-services/occupational-standards/download-ros> or https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B1w3EHAUdpCLU00tamNWLvNtVfK/view?resourcekey=0-Aix9a6Klc1wcq4udfkq_gA

2. Prosecution and enforcement manuals for CARIFORUM member States:- Volume 1 Fisheries Prosecution Manual and Volume 2 Fisheries Enforcement Standard Operating Procedures Manual available at https://crfm.int/images/Fisheries_Enforcement_Manual.pdf and https://crfm.int/images/Fisheries_Prosecution_Manual.pdf
These manuals can easily be adapted for use in terrestrial sites.
3. Grenada Marine Protected Areas Rangers Standard Operational Procedures Manual available at [http://www.oas.org/en/sedi/dsd/biodiversity/ReefFix/GrenadaMPAWorkshop/GRENADA%20FISHERIES%20DIVISION%20STANDARD%20OPERATIONAL%20PROCEDURES%20MANUAL%202013%20-%203%20\(1\).pdf](http://www.oas.org/en/sedi/dsd/biodiversity/ReefFix/GrenadaMPAWorkshop/GRENADA%20FISHERIES%20DIVISION%20STANDARD%20OPERATIONAL%20PROCEDURES%20MANUAL%202013%20-%203%20(1).pdf)
4. Environmental Interpretation Manual for Protected Areas in the Mesoamerican Barrier Reef System Region available at <https://www.cbd.int/doc/pa/tools/Environmental%20interpretation%20manual%20or%20protected%20areas%20in%20the%20MBRS.pdf>

A fourth approach to training that ought to be considered, is through the training of volunteer community researchers, especially youth by staff within the government agencies and NGOs responsible for biodiversity conservation, who have the requisite expertise. Community researchers can be utilized to assist PA managers in scientific research and monitoring of selected ecosystems and species. This approach has been used with great success in Belize. Participants have been trained in SCUBA diving, GPS use and basic GIS analysis, emergency first response, basic environment science, including basic coral reef ecology, land-sea interconnectivity, and the impact of human activities, scientific monitoring and assessment. The following ecosystem components can be monitored by these trained volunteers: water quality, coral, seagrass, mangrove, fish and shellfish, birds, bats, terrestrial vegetation, invasive species, visitor use, etc.

The fifth approach to building capacity is through the availability of scholarships or grants that are made available to governments by foreign agencies, such as the British Chevening Scholarships. The United Nations agencies such as UNEP and UNDP may occasionally offer short training courses relevant to PA managers. AB has been the recipient of several sponsored training courses for example, through the UNEP/CAMPAM on MPA Management over the past 15 years. Additionally, the Antigua and Barbuda Board of Education manages finances generated by the Education Levy and provides bursaries and information about scholarships for Antigua and Barbuda nationals.

Budget

The Business and Sustainable Financing Plan for Antigua and Barbuda's System of Protected Areas 2021-2031, estimated that the annual costs for managing the existing system of

protected areas will be about USD3 million (XCD8.1 million) per annum, based on a Caribbean predictive model. The financing plan further estimated that with cost saving measures the annual costs could be reduced to approximately USD1.9 million (XCD5.1 million). It would be useful for the Protected Areas Coordinating Mechanism and the PA managers to identify the recurrent annual expenditures for all PAs, proposed annual development costs (equipment, materials, infrastructure, etc.), new staffing as proposed above, and cost for priority training of staff and volunteers. This will then give a more realistic annual cost for management of the system of protected areas. Once that operational budget is determined, the mechanisms proposed in the financing plan should be utilized to access the required funding.

Schedule of Key Activities

Table 6 below proposes a schedule for implementation of the major activities that will help to improve management effectiveness for Antigua and Barbuda’s system of protected areas. These activities are: Quality assurance, staffing, training and budget acquisition.

Table 6. Proposed schedule for implementation of activities to support the system of protected areas.

Key Activities for Implementation	Year 1	Year2	Year3	Year 4	Year5
Quality Assurance					
1. Technical assistance obtained for developing quality management system					
2. Quality management system developed and approved					
3. Quality management procedures documented and used by staff					
Staffing					
4. Human resources needs assessment completed					
5. Job specifications prepared					
6. Priority staffing needs of each PA site determined					
7. New staff recruited					
Training					
8. Training agenda developed for PA staff					
9. Develop training exchange programme					
10. Sign MoUs with agencies to deliver training					
11. Identify free online and paid courses for PA staff					
12. Online training courses undertaken					
13. Identify community volunteers for training					
14. Identify topics for training and in-house trainers					

Key Activities for Implementation	Year 1	Year2	Year3	Year 4	Year5
15. Conduct training of volunteers					
16. Deploy volunteers					
Budget					
17. Determine annual cost for managing PAs					
18. Select mechanisms proposed in the financing plan to secure funds in excess of annual government subventions.					
19. Apply funding to staff recruitment, equipment, materials, etc.					

Monitoring and Evaluation

Quarterly work plans should be developed by the PA managers and these should be reviewed by the Protected Areas Coordinating Mechanism and advice provided as appropriate. These workplans will contain elements of the implementation plan that staff think are feasible for the period, based on the human resource capacity, financial allocations and administrative challenges of the PA agencies/entities. Guidelines on workplan preparation are available at <https://www.wikihow.com/Write-a-Work-Plan> and <https://www.fool.com/the-blueprint/work-plan/>.

Progress on implementation should be reviewed quarterly or at least twice per year so that difficulties in execution of activities could be identified and resolved and slippage in timely outputs could be controlled. Progress can be measured by achievement of tangible outputs within a given timeline.

An annual evaluation of the implementation including its effectiveness could be conducted if no other periodic review of implementation is undertaken as outlined in the preceding paragraph. Administratively, the legally designated management authorities for these various PAs, should each ensure that the appropriate monitoring and management is achieved, with the PA site manager having the ultimate responsibility for planning and executing the monitoring programme.

At the end of the 5-year period of this implementation plan, it is recommended that an independent evaluation be undertaken to determine the extent to which the objectives were achieved, challenges that impacted on the implementation of the plan, approaches used to overcome or mitigate those challenges, innovative management approaches, emerging issues, recommendations and lessons that should be learnt. This evaluation will inform a new implementation plan for the next 5-year cycle.

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APPENDIX 1

LIST OF STAKEHOLDERS

Antigua and Barbuda PA Systems Plan Revision

Stakeholders Consulted – including those who reviewed draft documents and participated in the online discussions on the draft documents, who submitted comments and completed questionnaires related to this assignment.

November 2020 to November 2021

Name	Dept/Institution	Position
Helena Jeffery Brown	Dept of Environment	Technical Coordinator
Katecia Thompson	Dept of Environment	Biodiversity Project Coordinator
Jenniael Flermius	Dept of Environment	Biodiversity Apprentice
Jason P. Williams	Dept of Environment	Data Manager
Anik Jarvis	Dept of Environment	GIS Apprentice
Janeil Johnston	Dept of Environment	GIS Officer
Owolabi Elabanjo	Agriculture Ext. Division	Chief Agricultural Extension Officer (Ag)
Camilla Wallace	Forestry Unit	Forestry Officer
Adriel Thibou	Forestry Unit	Forestry Officer
Christopher Waters	National Parks Authority	Assistant Manager, Heritage Department
Ruleta Camacho Thomas	National Parks Authority	Natural Resource and Environmental Management-Senior Advisor
Ogden Burton	Codrington Lagoon National Park	Manager
Arica Hill	Environmental Awareness Group	Executive Director
Shanna Challenger	Environmental Awareness Group	Off-shore Island Coordinator
Refica Attwood	Executive Director	Wallings Nature Reserve

APPENDIX 2

Summary of the Location and Key Features of the Protected Areas
Listed in Table 1.

Declared Protected Areas

Name: Cades Bay Marine Reserve

Year declared: 1999

Area: 1,670 ha. The area bounded seaward by:-

Lat.17° 00' 18"N and Long. 061° 50' 05"W to
Lat.17° 00' 00"N and Long. 061° 49' 59"N to
Lat.17° 00' 00" N and Long. 061° 54' 02"W to
Lat.17° 01' 37" N and Long. 061° 54' 02"W to
Lat.17° 01' 37" N and Long. 061° 53' 25"W;

and landwards by the landward edges of the mangrove and wetland systems from Johnson's Point to Carlisle Bay and Claremont, Old Road, in the Parish of St. Mary's, where they exist and the coastline where they do not.

Reason for declaration: To create sustainable production of fish and protection of ecosystems.

Key Features: The area contains three main important ecosystems namely coral reefs, seagrass beds and related ecosystems (beaches, mangroves, lagoons and other wetlands), within the Southwestern watershed of Antigua. Kayaking, snorkelling, diving, fishing, farming and coastal resort use are some of the activities that take place there, as reported in the 2012 management plan for this site (Wynne, S. 2012).

Name: Diamond Reef and Salt Fish Reef Marine Protected Area

Year declared: 1973

Area: 1,450 ha. Bound by the area within:

Lat. 17° 11' 5.960" N and Long. 61° 49' 30.066" W
Lat. 17° 11' 5.879" N and Long. 61° 53' 12.018" W
Lat. 17° 12' 17.986" N and Long. 61° 53' 11.960" W
Lat. 17° 12' 17.880" N and Long. 61° 49' 29.985" W

Reason for declaration: No Take Zone to ensure sustainability of the lobster and conch fisheries.

Key Features: This area is an important habitat for aquatic species such as the Parrot Fish and is very crucial for the development of other juvenile species.

Name: Northeast Marine Management Area (Marine Protected Area)

Year declared: 2005

Area: 10, 800 ha. The NEMMA is defined in relation to the Waters of Antigua and Barbuda bounded seaward by:

1. Lat. 17° 10' 14"N and Long. 061° 48' 16"W
Lat. 17° 12' 09.26"N and Long. 061° 48' 14.87"W to
Lat. 17° 06' 34.72"N and Long. 061° 38' 36.59"W to
Lat. 17° 06' 47.07"N and Long. 061° 38' 36.89"W to
Lat. 17° 02' 48.23"N and Long. 061° 40' 26.74"W
2. The landward edges of mangroves and wetland systems or the line of permanent vegetation which ever applies;
3. The following offshore islands:
Prickly Pear Island Long Island Guiana Island

Green Island	Great Bird Island	Maiden Island
Crump Island	Pelican Island	Galley Island
Major Rat Island	Nanny Island	York Island
Galley Island	Minor Little	Bird Island
Laviscounts Island	Codrington Island	Jenny island
Hells Gate Island	Bird Island	Exchange Island
Monocle Point Island	Round Island	Rabbit Island
Read Head Island	Hawes Island	Little Island
Lobster Island	Lobster Island Extension	

And any other unnamed islands or rocky outcrops.

Reason for declaration: Multi-use PA for conservation of endemic, rare and globally important wildlife, fisheries protection and recreation/tourism.

Key Features: The entire area and surrounding environment is a rich complex of fringing, linear and patch reefs blended with extensive seagrass beds and sand channels to form a healthy, diverse ecosystem of significant size and comprised of many habitat types. Coral reefs dominate the outer bay and offshore areas extensively. Patch reefs are found spotting the middle of the inner bay along with bedrock encrusted coral along significant areas of the shoreline. The unique island vegetation, coastal hedge and shrublands, the mangrove wetlands and salt ponds and the extensive combination of marine communities makes this a particularly important area for preservation. The shallow and enclosed nature contribute to nursery characteristics important to species richness and abundance (Jackson, 2008 and Tropical Ecosystem Consulting, 2010).

Name: Goat Point Sanctuary

Year declared: 2014

Area: 1,818 ha. Goat Point Sanctuary includes all waters within the polygon starting at Point A, a water-based mark on the one league boundary, at coordinates 17.7408°N and 61.8578°, and then proceeding as follows –

- a. from Point A, the boundary shall due north to Point B, a water-based mark on the one league boundary, at coordinates 17.7762°N and 61.8578°W;
- b. from Point B, the boundary shall follow the one league boundary to Point C, a water-based mark on the one league boundary, at coordinates 17.7704°N and 61.8198°W;
- c. from Point C, the boundary shall run in a straight-line due south to Point D, a water-based mark at coordinates 17.7305°N and 61.8198°W; and
- d. from Point D, the boundary shall run in a straight line back to Point A.

Reason for declaration: The no-take marine reserve was created to ensure the sustainability of Barbuda's marine resources.

Key Features: Goat point sanctuary is marine reserve and habitat for healthy red and buttonwood mangrove species. It is an important tidal flushing point.

Name: Low Bay Sanctuary

Year declared: 2014

Area: 4,872 ha. Low Bay Sanctuary includes all waters within the polygon starting at Point A, a land-based mark with geographical coordinates 17.6576°N and 61.857°W, and then proceeding as follows—

- a. from Point A, the boundary shall run in a straight line due west to Point B, a water-based mark on the one league boundary, with geographical coordinates at 17.6576°N and 61.9163°W;
- b. from Point B, the boundary shall follow the one league boundary to Point C, a water-based mark on the one league boundary, at coordinates 17.5796°N and 61.9109°W;
- c. from Point C, the boundary shall run in a straight line due east to Point D, a land-based mark at coordinates 17.5796°N, 61.8579°W; and
- d. from Point D, the boundary shall follow the contours of the coastline back to Point A.

Reason for declaration: The no-take marine reserve was created to ensure the sustainability of Barbuda's marine resources.

Key Features: Marine ecosystems associated with the protection of the fishery.

Name: Palastar Sanctuary

Year declared: 2014

Area: 320 ha. Palastar Sanctuary includes all waters within the polygon starting at Point A, a land-based mark at Coco Point with geographical coordinates 17.5428°N and 61.7676°W, and then proceeding as follows—

- a. from Point A, the boundary shall run in a straight line to Point B, a land-based mark, with geographical coordinates 17.5436°N and 61.7335°W;
- b. from Point B, the boundary shall run in a straight line due south to Point C, a water-based mark, at coordinates 17.5244°N and 61.7335°W;
- c. from Point C, the boundary shall run in a straight line to Point D, a water-based mark on the one league boundary, at coordinates 17.4975°N and 61.7836°W;
- d. from Point D, the boundary shall follow the one league boundary to Point E, a water-based mark on the one league boundary, at coordinates 17.5131°N and 61.8069°W; and
- e. from Point E, the boundary shall run in a straight line back to Point A.

Reason for declaration: No take zone to ensure sustainability fisheries resources and wreck diving as tourist attraction.

Key Features: a very important habitat for parrot fish and coral species.

Name: Two Foot Bay Sanctuary

Year declared: 2014

Area: 4,839 ha. Two Foot Bay Sanctuary includes all waters within the polygon starting at Point A, a land-based mark with geographical coordinates 17.6836°N and 61.7807°W, and then proceeding as follows –

- a. from Point A, the boundary shall run in a straight line due east to Point B, a water-based mark on the one league boundary, at coordinates 17.6836°N and 61.7122°W;
- b. from Point B, the boundary shall follow the one league boundary to Point C, a water-based mark on the one league boundary, at coordinates 17.6132°N and 61.6826°W;
- c. from Point C, the boundary shall run in a straight line due west to Point D, a land-based mark, at coordinates 17.6136°N and 61.7345°W; and

- d. from Point D, the boundary shall follow the contours of the coastline back to Point A.

Reason for declaration: The no-take marine reserve was created to ensure the sustainability of Barbuda's marine resources.

Key Features: very unique location at the northern base of the highlands in a transitional area between upland and low wetlands to the North. The area is isolated, favored with multiple habitat types nearby and lies along a significant offshore reef. Minimal recreational use occurs here where the cliff habitat begins and runs linearly south along the coast. The site includes the highest point in Barbuda, consisting of important cave systems and rich biodiversity to include the red tortoise, and important cactus and bird species (such as the Barbuda Wobbler). It is famous for its caves, most importantly the Indian Cave, which has the only known petroglyphs on Barbuda. The marine component is important for fish and other aquatic biodiversity.

Name: Codrington Lagoon National Park

Year declared: 2005

Area: 6,735 ha. This park is bounded seaward in the west by the Caribbean Sea and landward in the east by the Martello Tower moving northwards past the Sand Ground Plantation, the Cemetery along the River Road to the intersection of the Cut line, along the south of the Codrington Airstrip, along the western portion of the Village and towards the All In Well, from the All In Well the boundary runs along the Fishing Creek Road, the Tidal flats and ends at the Trig Station "Ba 14" located approximately halfway between Fishing Creek and Hog Point.

Reason for declaration: Protection of wetland habitat and marine biodiversity; lagoon tours for recreation and tourism. Also a Ramsar site (#1488).

Key Features: The Park features a large salt-water mangrove-fringed lagoon system that extends 16.5 kms along Barbuda's west and north-west coast, and includes two lagoons: Codrington Lagoon, which is the larger, and Goat Island Flash, which is smaller and shallower. One of the iconic features of the Lagoon is the presence of a breeding colony of about 5,000 pairs of magnificent frigatebirds (*Fregata magnificens*), the largest such colony in the Caribbean and among the largest in the world.

Name: Devil's Bridge National Park

Year declared: 2007

Area: 99 ha. This National Park is located from point 189030 N, 63925 E, eastwards 1.75 km to point 189030 N, 64100 E out at sea, thence North 1.2 km to 189150 N, 641000 E, thence West-southwest mid-channel 2.0 km to point 189050 N, 63940 E, then returning South 300 m to first point 189030 N, 63925 E.

Reason for declaration: Coastal site for recreation and tourism, Amerindian site, dry scrub woodland.

Key Features: Within the park there is remarkable example of seawater erosion. Devil's Bridge is a natural arch carved by the sea from soft and hard limestone ledges of the Antiguan formation. The open Atlantic Ocean view and foaming breaking waves are reported as impressive. A fringing coral reef is accessible from a small white sandy beach near the Devil's Bridge.

Name: Fort Barrington National Park

Year declared: 2008

Area: 34.5 ha. The Notice of Declaration in the National Gazette defines this national park From a point East 411700, North 1893750, South 450 m to East 411700, North 1893300, thence East 300 m point East 412000, North 1893300, thence North 100 m to point East 412000, North 1893400, thence East 600 m to point East 412600, North 1893400, thence North 350 m to point East 412600, North 1894050, thence returning to the starting point 900 m West to East 411700, North 1893750.

Reason for declaration: Historic fort, a small Amerindian site, and the remains of the Andes shipwreck inside Deep Bay.

Key Features: Ruins of a fort built in the 17th century atop Goat Hill. Scenic views.

Name: Greencastle Hill National Park

Year declared: 2007

Area: 35 ha. This site is located from point East 416440, North 1887800, South 420 m to point East 4116390, North 1887385, thence Southwest 252 m to point East 416200, North 1887200, thence Northwest 355 m to point East 414620, North 1887200, thence North 350 m to East 415700, North 1887500, thence 740 m East returning to point 416440 East, North 1887800.

Reason for declaration: Amerindian site, stone “megaliths”, scenic value.

Key Features: The hill offers scenic views of Antigua and has rhomboidal and polygonal stone columns at the site including ‘megaliths’ and ‘sacrificial slabs’ which are considered by some authorities as the remains of a prehistoric astronomical observatory and temple. The site also includes the grave of the Governor of the Leeward islands (1948-1950), who was also the son of a former British Prime Minister (NPA, 2002a).

Name: Nelson’s Dockyard National Park

Year declared: 1984

Area: 4,068 ha (including 1811 ha marine and 2257 ha terrestrial).

The Nelson’s Dockyard National Park consists of all that land to be specified, delineated and particularly described by Order made by the Minister after consultation with the Authority and published in the Gazette situate at and known as Nelson’s Dockyard, Shirley Heights, Dows Hill, and all lands adjacent to such lands or in the vicinity thereof (save and except therefore Clarence House and the appurtenances and land therewith usually occupied) as well as all land adjacent to English Harbour and Falmouth Harbour or in the vicinity thereof. Described generally as that area of land along the coast line from Carlisle Bay to Mamora Bay which includes the watershed and visual areas along that coast line, significant historic and natural sites in the vicinity of Nelson’s Dockyard, and wilderness area east of Falmouth Harbour.

Reason for declaration: Preservation, protection and management of the natural, scenic, historical and cultural heritage of the dockyard and surrounding areas.

Key Features: A working Georgian era naval dockyard with historic buildings which was inscribed as a UNESCO World Heritage Site in 2016 as the "Antigua Naval Dockyard and Related Archaeological Sites". Hiking trails, taking you through some of the most scenic places in the country including historic ruins, complex geological features, and different ecosystems.

Proposed PAs

Name: Boggy Peak National Park

Area: 1,039 ha. There are 435 unique points that define the BPNP boundary.

Reason for declaration: Maintenance of the ecological character and function of the area and provision of benefits to local, national and international stakeholders.

Key Features: This National Park is home to some of Antigua's rarest birds and is a haven for many migrants on their annual migrations from the arctic and temperate zones in the north. It houses the country's only two International Birding Areas (IBAs) – the Christian Valley IBA (AG009) and the adjoining Walling's Forest IBA (AG008) which together, represent Antigua's wet forested ecosystem. Additionally, the site has the highest point on the island (402 m) and the hilly terrain has important forest communities, waterways, watersheds, waterfalls and ponds. The park holds great cultural and historic value dating back to the days of slavery and parts of the fertile areas are important for agricultural production.

Name: Wallings Reservoir

Area: 0.5 ha. It's centrepiece is located at lat. 17° 2' 6.798" N and long. 61° 49' 30.231" W.

Reason for declaration: Protection of the historic Wallings reservoir

Key Features: The Wallings reservoir is over 100 years old and functional.

Name: Wallings Nature Reserve

Area: 680 ha (currently 105 ha is managed by the Wallings Nature Reserve Inc.).

Wallings Nature Reserve is defined as the block and parcel #56-1882A-37.

Reason for declaration: Watershed protection and habitat conservation for wildlife.

Key Features: The literature and research indicate the Wallings Forest/Fig Tree area is an excellent example of a mature and to some extent undisturbed upland forest ecosystem. Survey literature all point to the occurrence of critical plant and animal species associated with the area. Several important vegetation Alliances and Community Associations are found throughout the mountainous area. The area of forest is large and mixed with a pattern of open grazing areas and contiguous with other adjacent forested areas. The expansive forested south east mountainous area acts as core wildlife habitat for multiple species. Antigua's only endemic bird is the Broad-winged Hawk (*Buteo platypterus insulicola*), which nests in the tall trees and rocky cliffs of Wallings.

Name: Redonda Ecosystem Reserve

Area: 29,587 hectares of which approximately 60 hectares comprises the island itself.

Redonda is located at 16°56'N; 62°21'W and it lies 56 km Southwest of Antigua, 22 km Northwest of Montserrat and 32 km Southeast of Nevis. Redonda is 1.6 km long, 0.5 km wide and rises to nearly 400m.

Reason for declaration: Effective protection of biological diversity, preservation of historical values, and demonstration of the ridge to reef principle.

Key Features: The protected area encompasses the entire island of Redonda and the surrounding seas 1 km beyond the continental shelf (500 m depth contour). Redonda is a global Key Biodiversity Area because of its endemic and globally threatened reptiles and other species. The island and its nearshore waters are also a globally Important Bird Area (AG001), covering 720 hectares, because of the regionally significant colonies of magnificent frigatebirds, masked boobies, red-footed boobies and brown boobies.

Name: Christian Valley

Area: 1759 ha. The Christian Valley Registration Section is composed of all parcels within the following blocks:

52-1481A, 52-1583A, 52-1680D, 52-1681A, 52-1681E, 52-1683B, 52-1780C, 52-1781E, 52-1783A, 52-1785A, 52-1984C, and 52-1984F.

Reason for declaration: This site will not now be declared separately as an independent protected area since it falls almost entirely within the Shekerley Mountain Management Area (SMMA).

Key Features: Major watersheds and productive agricultural lands.

Name: Shekerley Mountain Management Area (SMMA)

Area: 2271 ha. The SMMA is the area bound by the following points:

- (a) lat. 17° 2' 17.761" N and long 61° 49' 20.462" W to
- (b) lat. 17° 2' 3.482" N and long 61° 49' 7.699" W to
- (c) lat. 17° 2' 2.136" N and long 61° 49' 7.619" W to
- (d) lat. 17° 1' 15.051" N and long 61° 49' 14.599" W to
- (e) lat. 17° 1' 15.370" N and long 61° 49' 17.765" W to
- (f) lat. 17° 1' 32.902" N and long 61° 49' 33.944" W to
- (g) lat. 17° 1' 38.574" N and long 61° 49' 42.572" W to
- (h) lat. 17° 1' 38.058" N and long 61° 50' 2.525" W to
- (i) lat. 17° 1' 35.996" N and long 61° 50' 19.242" W to
- (j) lat. 17° 1' 26.198" N and long 61° 50' 42.431" W to
- (k) lat. 17° 1' 32.902" N and long 61° 51' 48.762" W to
- (l) lat. 17° 1' 45.793" N and long 61° 52' 9.793" W to
- (m) lat. 17° 1' 50.433" N and long 61° 52' 45.385" W to
- (n) lat. 17° 2' 0.230" N and long 61° 53' 10.192" W to
- (o) lat. 17° 2' 11.058" N and long 61° 53' 17.742" W to
- (p) lat. 17° 2' 13.120" N and long 61° 53' 17.202" W to
- (q) lat. 17° 2' 19.823" N and long 61° 53' 6.956" W to
- (r) lat. 17° 2' 30.135" N and long 61° 52' 53.474" W to
- (s) lat. 17° 2' 44.572" N and long 61° 52' 41.610" W to
- (t) lat. 17° 3' 1.070" N and long 61° 52' 24.354" W to
- (u) lat. 17° 3' 43.861" N and long 61° 52' 1.704" W to
- (v) lat. 17° 4' 24.588" N and long 61° 51' 20.720" W to
- (w) lat. 17° 4' 19.433" N and long 61° 50' 51.599" W to
- (x) lat. 17° 3' 30.973" N and long 61° 50' 29.489" W to
- (y) lat. 17° 3' 16.022" N and long 61° 50' 14.928" W to
- (z) lat. 17° 2' 56.946" N and long 61° 49' 57.132" W to
- (a2) lat. 17° 2' 42.509" N and long 61° 49' 39.336" W to
- (b2) lat. 17° 2' 38.900" N and long 61° 49' 38.258" W and back to point (a).

Reason for declaration: To preserve and protect the historical, natural and cultural heritage of SMMA for present and future generations, and immediate communities, by building resilience of, and effectively managing its endemic biodiversity and unique landscape.

Key Features: One of the best examples of moist evergreen closed canopy forest on the island and harbour the last remaining tropical forest in the country. The area encompasses other protected areas, forest reserves, two of Antigua and Barbuda's ten Key Biodiversity Areas, and the only two International Birding Areas (IBA's) in the country. The SMMA is

home to several important flora and fauna including Antigua's only endemic bird, the Broad-winged Hawk (*B. platypterus insulicola*) where it nests in the tall trees and rocky cliffs of the region. It partially comprises three major watersheds on the island, Christian Valley, Cades Bay and Body Ponds. In addition to its natural value, the SMMA has immense historic and cultural value as a place of refuge for escaping Maroon slaves, home to several Amerindian historic sites, outstanding megaliths, and ancient reservoirs.

APPENDIX 3

**GUIDELINE: Preparing Protected Area Management Plans
for Antigua and Barbuda**

GUIDELINE

Preparing Protected Area Management Plans for Antigua and Barbuda

Floyd Homer
Revised 15th January, 2021

This document is a deliverable for the Department of Environment, Ministry of Health, Wellness and the Environment, Antigua and Barbuda under The Path to 2020 Project, that aims to implement Objective 1 of Antigua and Barbuda's National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (2014 – 2025): A national system, including protected areas, for the management and conservation of biodiversity conservation is developed and established.

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Guideline for Preparing Protected Area Management Plans for Antigua and Barbuda

Floyd Homer

15th January, 2021

Purpose and Approach

This document is prepared as an output under contract with the Department of Environment, Government of Antigua and Barbuda for the revision of the Systems Plan for Protected Areas in Antigua and Barbuda (2010).

A review of a few local, regional and international protected area (PA) management plans was undertaken, so that recommendations could be made for a suitable guideline for Antigua and Barbuda (AB). Five of the better PA management plans were selected for review because they reflected a range of styles, content and complexity, including issues relevant to AB, such as institutional and legislative capacity, resource uses and conflicts. The selection of these plans was of course subjective and also based on my experience in working on protected areas issues in several of the countries in the Caribbean. The Guidelines for Marine Protected Areas produced by the IUCN-World Conservation Union in 1999 as part of the World Commission on Protected Areas, Best Practice Protected Areas Guidelines Series, is a reference document that is used by many countries globally, was also examined and later adapted in this exercise.

The PA management plans utilised in this review were:

- Bonaire National Marine Park Management Plan, 2006
- Florida Keys National Marine Sanctuary Revised Management Plan (USA), 2007
- Turneffe Atoll Management Plan (Belize), 2012
- Grand Anse Marine Protected Area Management Plan (Grenada), 2016
- Sherkeley Mountain Management Area: Management Plan, (Antigua and Barbuda) 2020

Key Elements of PA Management Plans

In preparing any management plan, it must be clear for whom the plan is intended. Who are expected to be the primary users of the PA management plan? How will the plan be used?

The PA management plans listed above, range in size from 39 pages to 382 pages. It is unlikely that most PA stakeholders will read a very large document. Researchers, consultants and donor staff are often the types of persons who would most likely read large PA documents. PA Managers on the other hand, generally believe they already know the issues and background information; were likely participants in the preparation of the PA management plan, and therefore usually focus only on the key management activities and implementation schedule proposed for the PA site.

The purpose of the management plan must be defined, with sufficient background information so that any reader understands the context, issues or conflicts that require attention. Clearly articulated objectives for the plan are also needed, as well as activities designed to achieve these objectives. The identification of resource requirements and an implementation plan will comprise the final core elements of the PA management plan.

Background Information

Many of the PA management plans provided a lot of interesting background information, much of which is not directly relevant to the issues or management activities. The target audience for the management plan is sometimes not clearly stated. Explanations on coral reef and wetland ecosystems functioning are sometimes provided, but are not necessary for a management plan. In many cases, site specific data or information on geology, currents, habitats, species and resource uses are often not available or accessible, so information, where it exists for other areas on the island or for neighbouring islands are used. Occasionally, data that is over 10-15 years old were cited, because recent data was unavailable. Management prescriptions based on old data may not be applicable to the current status of the resource or habitat.

Management Issues and Implementation Plan

A range of management issues are identified in all of the plans reviewed, with several of them outside of the control of the PA management entity, but under the jurisdiction of other State agencies. Land based sources of pollution, discharge of sewage, maritime traffic, and coastal development are prime examples of such issues. Some management plans seem to have too many objectives to be achieved over the period of the plan (usually 5 years), especially in the context of resource limitations and inadequate institutional infrastructure. The objectives need to be measurable and activities to achieve these objectives need to be ambitious but realistic in terms of resource constraints, particularly in the early years of implementation. A 5-year period for a management plan is considered adequate. In the Caribbean, the length of time it takes to get approvals and financing and the bureaucracy involved, often seem not to influence the design timelines in some plans. This leads to long delays in the implementation schedule and many of the proposed actions not getting done within the stipulated timeline. Occasionally, the failure of overly ambitious financing proposals, reallocation of the State's resources, and the recruitment of inappropriately trained and dedicated staff (or lack of recruitment of appropriate staff) reduce the effectiveness of any implementation plan.

The implementation plan should therefore be developed by the PA management agency based on the management plan, when staffing and financial resources are available.

Guide for the preparation of a PA Management Plan

The following template is adapted from that promoted by the IUCN in its Guidelines for Marine Protected Areas and modified based on the review of the sample management plans and experience with PAs in the Caribbean. The management plan can be written by anyone with sufficient expertise or experience in management planning or protected areas management. Either staff of the government agency responsible for PAs, the PA management entity or consultants may be utilized in the preparation of the management plan.

TITLE PAGE

This includes:

- The name of the area subject to the plan and its status;

- The words MANAGEMENT PLAN;
- The name of the agency/agencies responsible for implementing the plan;
- The date when the plan was prepared and the period/duration of the plan.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY PAGE

On this page are summarized:

- The reasons why the plan was prepared;
- The period of time to which it applies;
- The principal provisions of the plan; and
- The estimated budget.

CONTENTS PAGE

The headings of the body of the plan are listed here against the appropriate page numbers. It may be preferable to list only the main headings, but sub-headings are usually included.

BODY OF THE PLAN

- **Introduction**

An indication of why the site was chosen as a protected area and why a management plan for the site is needed.

- **Resource Description**

This section provides information on the following aspects of the areas to be protected. Maps or satellite imagery will be an important feature of this section.

- Name of Area and Location

To include the geographic location; latitudes and longitudes (preferably on a map); inclusive of GPS coordinates and surface area (square kilometres, hectares or other units of area).

- Ecosystem Description

A general description of the ecosystems and ecosystem services at the target site, to include key elements based on existing literature or site visit. In this section the non-living of physical features of the area are also described. Maps or diagrams should be included.

- Conservation Status

This should indicate the area's degree of naturalness, aesthetic values, degree and nature of threats (if any), jurisdiction(s) and present ownership. The degree

of habitat
representativeness should also be indicated.

- Access and Context

The surrounding land or sea and access routes to the area are described, in addition to the character and use of contiguous areas, indicating their potential use as buffer zones.

- History and Development

This section contains a summary account of direct and peripheral human involvement

in the area. This section may be divided into several sub-sections e.g.:

- Archaeology

- A summary description of the archaeological information on the site, which may influence management activities.

- Historical relics

- This sub-section should identify submerged wrecks and any other submerged structures of historic interest for marine sites and derelict structures/machinery /ruins or monuments for terrestrial sites.

- Current human use and development

- In this section, the current use of the area by subsistence, artisanal, commercial and recreational users, tourists and others is discussed. It is most important to establish who the users are, where they conduct their activities, at what times of the year, and for how long, and the social and economic importance of their use. Any cultural importance associated with the site should also be included.

- Aquatic

- Bathymetry

- A map showing isobaths is needed. The depth of water can provide an important insight into the dynamics of the system.

- Tides and Dominant currents

- A description of the tidal regime and resultant currents and water movements associated with phases of the tidal cycle and on a seasonal basis.

- Water quality, including salinity, turbidity and other important parameters
Measurements of salinity, turbidity and any major pollutant levels in all seasons are desirable.
 - Freshwater inputs
Rivers, streams, seasonal waterfalls and estuarine areas. Watersheds and associated ground water reservoirs.
- Climate
 - Precipitation
Overview, past and potential impact on management.
 - Temperature
Overview, past and potential impact of sea temperatures on marine resources or ambient temperature range for terrestrial areas.
 - Winds/storms/hurricanes
Overview, past and potential impact on resources and management.
- Plant life
This section should contain at least a description of dominant terrestrial/marine plant life, and wherever possible a comprehensive summary of the plant community and related environmental factors, such as the depth or elevation of occurrence, together with any botanical features that may have special scientific, recreational or other interest. Phytoplankton could be included if information is available. Plant species identified in the area should be listed in an appendix.
- Animal life
As a minimum, a description of the dominant or common fauna is required, with an account of their ecological relationships if known. Include sections on Mammals, Reptiles, Amphibians, Fish, Birds, Invertebrates and Zooplankton as appropriate. A separate appendix should list the species.
- Miscellaneous
This can be a varied section that includes those matters which do not fit under any of the other descriptions of the plan, e.g. valuable mineral or physical resources. Each plan will be site specific and could therefore have features or problems that are not encountered in other plans.

- **Description of Management Issues**

A summary of past, present and possible future threats and management conflicts should follow.

- Historic and current conflicts
A brief statement of any historic or current conflicts between uses or user groups.
- Pollution
Include point and non-point sources of external pollution within the area and in nearby areas, e.g. runoff, sewage inputs, fish processing/abattoir, pesticide use, garbage dumps, industrial pollution and pollution from tourism and shipping.
- Future demand
Estimate future demand for recreational and other uses, and if applicable, future pollution loading, proposed developments and other negative impacts.
- Potential conflicts
Potential conflicts specific to the area within and close to the boundary of the PA should be described. Any potential conflicts due to external influences, including the setting up of Free/Economic Zones, should also be identified. Unresolved questions of jurisdiction between levels of government especially in the intertidal environment or at marinas should be highlighted and, if appropriate, solutions suggested. This should include review of sectoral development plans and proposed projects that could affect the area.

- **Policy and Legislative Framework**

This section provides a description of the key policies and legislation that are relevant to the management of the protected area. Deficiencies in legislation with respect to management issues at the site should be noted. Where feasible, the legislation that prevails in the event of conflict between the provisions of different enactments should be identified. Implications for the protective status of the area should be identified.

- **Management Objectives**

- Objectives
The goal of protecting the area is briefly reiterated. The objectives of management are stated clearly. If the area is to be subdivided, sub-objectives should be stated

for each
zone or subdivision of the managed area.

The IUCN PA category may be proposed and included here after the objectives have been agreed by stakeholders

- Zoning (Maps are essential here)

Zoning must be easy to understand both from the point of view of the manager and the managed. This section should explain why a particular area has been given a zone classification and what activities are permitted and prohibited within each zone. The aim should be to keep the zoning arrangements as simple as possible, consistent with avoiding unnecessary restriction on human activities.

Special habitats or wildlife areas such as a seagrass bed, fish nursery or a turtle rookery, bird nesting sites, etc. may require additional management provisions, such as seasonal closures or permanent restrictions over access. Unusual prescriptions may be needed in the short term and these should be described in this section.

- Key activities to achieve the objectives may be described under the foregoing sections.

- Installation and Maintenance

Description of the PA infrastructure and equipment that will need to be procured, installed and maintained, especially for boundary and zone demarcation, as well as moorings. Access roads, interpretation centre, signage, trails, and other visitor use facilities should be considered.

- Surveillance and Enforcement

This section should describe any programme proposed to assess movement and activities of people and vessels, within and through the area and the use made of the area, including detection of apparent offences. This section should also outline the arrangements that will need to be made to apprehend and prosecute offenders in order to achieve an acceptable level of adherence to PA regulations. Include interpretative enforcement as a primary management tool.

- Restoration

Parts of a site, such as key habitats or historic infrastructure/buildings may be in need of restoration or rehabilitation. Details of the work to be undertaken and the timeline should be included here.

- Monitoring and Research

This section should describe any biological, environmental and usage monitoring or research programmes proposed for the area, when these

programmes will be done, who could carry them out and how they are to be used to improve management. The use of Citizen Science should also be considered for data gathering.

- **Awareness Building and Education**

This section should describe in-house programmes and co-operative arrangements with educational institutions, public associations and community groups to promote protection, wise use, public understanding and enjoyment of the PA. The use of social media and marketing strategy should be included here.

- **Training**

Description of key training needs, the levels of personnel that need training and a schedule for training is outlined.

- **Administration**

This section will be required to address the subjects of institutional arrangements, staffing, budget, etc.

- **Staffing**

The management plan should include institutional arrangements for managing the PA including an organisational chart, and show staffing needs and identify major functions. Volunteers, consultants and office staff involved in the planning process should also be identified, as this will provide a more accurate indication of staffing levels. Staffing deficiencies can be predicted and recommendations suggested.

- **Budget**

Anticipated costs and possible sources of funds should be identified with the aim of achieving a high level of self-financing for the period covered by the plan. A timeline for budgeted activities should also be proposed.

- **Quality Assurance**

The adoption of a quality management system is a strategic decision for an organization that can help to improve its overall performance, its ability to consistently provide products and services that meet customer and applicable statutory and regulatory requirements; and to enhance customer satisfaction. The outline of such a system based on best practice or international standards should be described.

- **Appendices**

- **Appendix 1: Plant Species**

A comprehensive list of plant species should be attempted for the first management

plan. As the process continues over the years, it is quite possible that new plant species will be discovered in the area. Plant names should be listed in broad taxonomic groups, with botanical and common names where possible. Local conservation status and the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species status should also be included.

- Appendix 2: Animal Species
Animal species should be listed in broad taxonomic groups: e.g. Mammals, Reptiles, Amphibians, Fish, Birds and Invertebrates and common names provided where possible. Local conservation status and the IUCN Red List Threatened Species status should also be included.
- Appendix 3: Special Features
This section could describe unusual or outstanding features of the area and could range from bird/whale migrations, wildlife feeding areas, spawning aggregations, scenic vistas to spiritual revelations and cultural beliefs.
- Appendix 4: Sources of Information
Information regarding the area will come from sources outside the PA Manager's regular information base. These should be identified and listed wherever possible, and include those of other government agencies, non-government organisations, individuals, consultants, overseas sources etc. that were consulted. A bibliography should be appended.

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APPENDIX 4

A Participatory Monitoring Method for Protected Areas in Antigua and Barbuda

A Participatory Monitoring Method for Protected Areas in Antigua and Barbuda

Floyd Homer
9th February, 2021

This report is a deliverable for the Department of Environment, Ministry of Health, Wellness and the Environment, Antigua and Barbuda under The Path to 2020 Project, that aims to implement Objective 1 of Antigua and Barbuda's National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (2014 – 2025): *A national system, including protected areas, for the management and conservation of biodiversity conservation is developed and established.*

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A Participatory Monitoring Method for Protected Areas in Antigua and Barbuda

Floyd Homer
9th February, 2021

Intent of this Document

The intent of this document is to provide a range of tried and tested key elements that the Protected Area (PA) Manager (or the PA Monitoring Team Leader) can select to develop their own monitoring programme. It is not intended to be too prescriptive, since different sites, management plans and PA management entities may have different priorities. PA Managers should be able to develop their own monitoring programmes based on the components outlined in the foregoing sections, the PA's priorities and existing resource constraints.

Why Monitor Protected Areas?

Protected areas (PA) are expected to be managed consistent with the requirements of a national policy, legislation or the management plan for the site. Monitoring provides the data that enables a determination of the status or the condition of resources, especially flora and fauna in and adjacent to the PA; the extent or changes in challenges, threats and impacts to the integrity of the PA; and the level of effectiveness of management interventions and compliance with regulations. Monitoring may also include elements related to public outreach and awareness building as well as overall administration of the PA system.

Monitoring can also serve to help the country meet its national obligations under multilateral environmental agreements. For example, with particular reference to protected areas, Article 8 of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) prescribes the following, among other things:

1. Use guidelines, tools and processes necessary for identifying, monitoring, regulating and conserving biological diversity; including the establishment and management of a system of protected areas.
2. Principles of conservation and sustainability should be put into practice both within and outside of protected areas.
3. Rehabilitate endangered species, prevent the introduction of alien species and control or eliminate those that threaten ecosystems or species.

Monitoring the implementation of those elements will help the government in reporting on its achievement of the articles under the CBD.

What is Participatory Monitoring?

Monitoring of protected areas in the past has generally been done by PA staff, scientists, researchers or consultants as a consequence of specific, project requirements or a research agenda. Increasingly, monitoring of flora and fauna has been undertaken by a range of stakeholders, including citizens or visitors and NGOs with an interest in specific habitats, species or groups of species, contributing to improved conservation measures. Participatory monitoring is the collaboration among a range of stakeholders to make observations, record measurements, photograph species and habitat change or impacts, etc., and often share these data with government agencies, researchers and other parties of interest to improve our understanding of local species and their habitats. This approach usually involves voluntary inputs through 'citizen science' while improving the frequency and extent of monitoring, which significantly lowers the cost of data collection for the agencies trusted with data management.

Who Should Ensure Protected Areas are Monitored?

Under the Environmental Protection and Management Act 2019 (EPMA), the Department of Environment (DoE) within the Ministry with responsibility for the Environment, which among other things, in the context of protected areas, is responsible for:

- Developing and implementing policies, programmes and plans for the effective management and conservation of the environment and natural resources consistent with the requirements of the Act;
- Coordinating environmental management functions performed by all governmental and non-governmental entities and statutory authorities in order to achieve the purposes of this Act;
- Undertaking the conservation, protection and management of biodiversity and the wildlife of Antigua and Barbuda including the management and licensing of biodiversity prospecting;
- Collaborating with the appropriate authority to ensure the effective administration and management of any area that is declared to be a protected area;
- Collaboration with the appropriate authority, in the development, implementation and monitoring of management plans and programmes for protected areas on Crown lands declared under this Act.

The DoE has the power to do all things necessary or convenient to be done for the carrying out of its functions under this Act. Therefore, the DoE has the responsibility to ensure that protected areas are monitored for the purposes for which they were established.

The following institutions have also declared PAs in the country over the past 55 years: The National Parks Authority (National Parks Act, 1984); Forestry Unit under the Ministry of

Agriculture (Forestry Act, revised 1989); Parks Commission under the Ministry of Lands (Public Parks Act, 1965); Fisheries Division under the Ministry of Agriculture (Marine Areas [Preservation and Enhancement] Act, 1974 and the Fisheries Act, revised 1989); and the Barbuda Council (Barbuda Land Act, 2007 and Barbuda (Coastal Zoning and Management) Regulations, 2014). Therefore, these agencies also have the responsibility to monitor and manage PAs declared under their legislation.

Administratively, the legally designated management authorities for these various PAs, should each ensure that the appropriate monitoring and management is achieved, with the PA site manager having the ultimate responsibility for planning and executing the monitoring programme.

What are the Key Things to be Monitored in PAs?

There are several major documents that provide the basis for the monitoring of various aspects of PAs in Antigua and Barbuda. These documents include national legislation, local PA management plans, national standards and key performance indicators, international guidance on assessing PA management effectiveness, and regional guidance on socioeconomic monitoring for managers of coastal resources. The following sections highlight a few examples for consideration.

Based on Key Legislation

Under the EPMA (2019), Section 54 identifies the main purposes for which protected areas will be established and managed in Antigua and Barbuda. Table 1 below summarises the management purpose and key elements that should be monitored.

Table 1. Summary of protected areas management purpose under the EPMA and key elements that should be monitored.

Management Purpose	Key Elements for Monitoring
1. Rehabilitation of any biosphere, flora and fauna or natural resource	Impacts on flora, fauna and natural resource; flora, fauna and natural resource inventory; rehabilitation plans; rehabilitation activities
2. Protection and conservation of the natural resources that offer an attraction to tourist visitors	Inventory of natural resources; visitor impacts; protection and conservation measures
3. Regulation of visitor activity to ensure that the carrying capacity of the natural resources is not exceeded	Determination of carrying capacity; visitor use including quantity and frequency; visitor impacts; visitor regulation measures
4. Protection and conservation of the marine resources within the foreshore reserve	Inventory of marine resources; impacts on marine resources; protection and conservation measures
5. Protection and preservation of areas of natural forest	Inventory of natural forest species and coverage; impacts on area of natural forest; protection and preservation measures
6. Forest Reserve's natural processes continue unaffected by human activity	Status of natural processes including impacts; protection measures
7. Protection of Forest Reserve's	Inventory of biological diversity; impacts on biodiversity;

biological diversity to the greatest possible extent	protection measures
8. Protection of natural resources and maintenance of natural processes in an undisturbed state in Nature Reserves	Status of natural resources; status of natural processes; impacts on the Nature Reserves; protection measures
9. Conservation, protection and management of the supply and quality of water available in Water Catchment Reserves	Status and quality of available water; conservation, protection and management measures
10. Conservation of the diversity and integrity of representative communities of wetland areas as specified the Convention on Wetlands of International Importance especially as Waterfowl Habitat	Coverage of wetland areas; inventory of wetland species richness and abundance; impacts on wetland areas; conservation measures
11. An area protected as a carbon sink managed in accordance with internationally accepted principles.	Acreage of carbon sink site; inventory of carbon storage species; carbon storage capacity of area; management measures

Based on Management Plan Objectives

Management plans prepared for specific PA sites will have several objectives and related activities designed to achieve these objectives. Monitoring the performance of these objectives during the period covered in the management plan and at the end of the implementation period will provide evidence on the level of achievement. For example, the management plan (2021-2026) for the Shekerley Mountains Management Area (SMMA) has several objectives under its four listed programmes. Table 2 provides the proposed key elements for monitoring that will illustrate how the performance of the objectives can be tracked for a particular PA.

Table 2. Management objectives of the Shekerley Mountains Management Area and proposed key elements for monitoring.

SMMA Management Objectives	Key Elements That Should Be Monitored
<u>Programme 1: Land Management and Use</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To ensure appropriate management structures are developed and implemented together with communities and key stakeholders • To develop and implement an effective land use management plan with clearly defined zones, regulations and guidelines for allowed activities • To control the impacts and spread of Invasive species • To develop and implement a comprehensive pollution and sustainable waste management programme 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Effectiveness of management structures ○ Effectiveness of implementation of management plan ○ Compliance with regulations and guidelines ○ Impacts of invasive species ○ Control of invasive species ○ Effectiveness of implementation of pollution and sustainable waste management programme ○ Levels of pollution from solid and liquid waste.
<u>Programme 2: Monitoring and Compliance</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To establish and implement an effective monitoring programme that includes monitoring biological and ecological indicators • To establish and implement an effective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Effectiveness of monitoring programme ○ Threats and impacts on biological and ecological indicators ○ Status of biological and ecological indicators ○ Effectiveness of compliance with regulations

compliance programme with appropriate regulations and guidelines	and guidelines
<u>Programme 3: Knowledge and Appreciation</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To increase knowledge and understanding of SMMA's natural and cultural values and history • To increase appreciation and pride in Antiguans and Barbudans of SMMA's natural and cultural values and history 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Effectiveness of implementation of education and awareness programme ○ Change in knowledge and understanding among target population ○ Change in appreciation and pride
<u>Programme 4: Sustainable Livelihoods and Recreation</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To develop and strengthen Eco-tourism and Heritage/Cultural Tourism opportunities in and around the SMMA • To increase opportunities for non-tourism related livelihoods that are financially sustainable and in harmony with nature • To enhance the natural space encouraging people to use it for enjoyment towards a healthy lifestyle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Number and types of opportunities developed and strengthened ○ Change in opportunities for non-tourism sustainable livelihoods ○ Change in natural space, including tourism infrastructure ○ Frequency and types of use of natural space

Based on PA Management Effectiveness

There are several guidelines or manuals available for monitoring protected areas. Perhaps the most common is the Management Effectiveness Tracking Tool (METT) developed by the World Wildlife Fund (WWF) and its partners. The METT has since become the most common protected areas management effectiveness tool, used in over 2,500 protected areas in at least 127 countries. The current version METT-4 now comes in an EXCEL spreadsheet for ease of data entry and analysis. It is designed with a range of key questions covering many elements that contribute to management effectiveness of a protected area and can be administered by anyone. Table 3 provides a summary of the elements examined in the METT-4.

Table 3. Summary of the elements examined in the METT-4 protected area management effectiveness tracking tool.

Management Component METT-4	Comments
1. Legal status	For areas with formal status; some areas may not yet have legal status.
2. Protected area objectives	The primary management objectives identified for the protected area.
3. Protected area regulations/controls	The existence of both legal regulations and customary controls.
4. Planning for adjacent land/sea use	Land and water use outside the protected area can significantly affect the protected area.
5. Protected area design	Issues to consider here include whether key species are adequately protected, whether it is large enough to support viable populations, and whether events outside the protected area could undermine its value.
6. Protected area boundary	Staff, stakeholders and rightsholders must recognise the boundary

demarcation	and people should know if they are encroaching the protected area.
7. Management planning	A formal management plan, written down and in the case of government-managed protected areas often also approved by the relevant department or ministry.
8. Regular work plan	An annual plan aimed at implementing components of the management plan.
9. Resource inventory	Referring primarily to biological and cultural values of the site.
10. Staff numbers	Sufficiency of staff to manage the site effectively and to fulfil its management objectives.
11. Knowledge and skills	People currently involved in managing the protected area (managers, rangers, support staff etc) should be able to manage the site effectively and fulfil its management objectives. If not, identify what additional training is required.
12. Current budget	The total amount of annual budget released and available for spending on the protected area.
13. Security of budget	Whether the budget is reliant on intermittent project funding or whether there is a reasonable chance of it being maintained over time.
14. Management of budget	Whether budget expenditure is properly planned and monitored through the year or if there are over- or under-spends.
15. Equipment and facilities	Status of equipment such as vehicles, communication systems, tools, uniforms and contributory materials like fuel. Facilities can be buildings and other important infrastructure that is needed to manage the protected area, such as guard posts, offices etc.
16. Law enforcement	Personal capacity (training, skills) and adequacy of equipment and infrastructure (vehicles, routes to access remote areas, etc.) along with an assessment of whether staff are familiar with laws, regulations and prosecution requirements.
17. Protection systems	Focuses particularly on enforcement, and will be applicable in places where there is pressure from poaching, encroachment, illegal mining etc.
18. Staff safety	Whether the safety of staff is considered in management, including the mitigation of threats where possible (e.g. through adequate equipment, training, etc) and the provision of support to minimise impacts when staff security is impacted (e.g. medical and life insurance, etc).
19. Research	Research work carried out by the protected area itself but more usually covers research by associates, volunteers, students, citizen science recorders and academics.
20. Monitoring and evaluation	Monitoring and evaluation of both the <i>management activities</i> of the protected area which impact on the condition of key values and the <i>threats</i> to the protected area.
21. Resource management	Activities in addition to enforcement needed to ensure effective conservation of critical habitats, species, ecological processes and cultural values.
22. Climate change	Focuses on management adaptations to predicted climate change, and how these are already being implemented.
23. Carbon capture	Methods for “preventing carbon loss” or increasing carbon storage in protected areas will depend on the ecosystems being managed.
24. Ecosystem services	This investigates both whether existing or potential ecosystem services are known and if so, whether some or all of them are being managed.
25. Education and awareness	Covers education both for learning establishments, such as school’s programmes, and also the provision of more general educational opportunities for local communities or recreational visitors.
26. State and commercial	Assessing the extent to which a protected area either co-operates

neighbours	with or remains isolated from the wider economy.
27. Commercial tourism operators	The extent of the protected area as a draw to tourists and thus a boost to the commercial trade.
28. Fees	The aim here is more to find out, where fees are an expected part of the protected area management, whether they are used to help management or simply disappear into the government and provide no support for the protected area.
29. Visitor facilities and services	Adequacy and appropriateness of visitor facilities.
30. Local communities	Assesses the level of influence that communities have on the overall decision-making process related to protected areas and the effect on local communities and their relationship and interaction with the protected area.
31. Livelihood benefits	Aimed explicitly at local communities. Benefits can include direct jobs, Payment for Ecosystem Service schemes, indirect benefits from increased tourism or sales to visitors, and other options such as tour guiding, etc.
32. Threats	Consider those threats identified in the threat assessment as having the greatest extent and severity; the focus is then on how the identified threats are being managed.
33. Connectivity	Focuses on functional connectivity of the protected area, addressing its direct linkages to other natural ecosystems, use of biological corridors, etc.
34. Condition of natural values	The current condition of the important natural values of the protected area. Ideally, the protected areas should have monitoring data relating to key species or habitats, and possibly access to remote sensing data to compare vegetation cover over time.
35. Condition of cultural values	Many protected areas contain important cultural values: sacred natural sites, pilgrimage routes, historic buildings, sites of historic significance, archaeological remains, etc.
36. Conservation status of key indicator species	Measure the condition of key indicator species regularly, using specific indicators and defined thresholds...the assumption here is that key indicator species for the site have been identified and their change in behaviour with changing habitat conditions are known.
37. Conservation status of habitats	Measure the condition of habitats regularly, using specific indicators and defined thresholds to determine status.

Based on National Standards and Key Performance Indicators

The National Standards and Key Performance Indicators for Antigua and Barbuda's Protected Areas were developed by a consultant in 2020 for the Department of Environment (Table 4). This document indicated that the IUCN Green List Standards were used as a key reference and is based the four main components for PA success: good governance, sound design and planning, effective management and conservation outcomes. The author of the document further indicated:

“...these Standards, along with Antigua and Barbuda's national and international commitments and objectives for Protected Areas which form the basis of the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) developed for Antigua and Barbuda's Protected Areas System... Protected Areas System Success Indicators Tracking Tool (PASS-ITT), the template developed for monitoring Antigua and Barbuda's PAs KPIs is similar to the METT in so far as it allows for

progress against the individual indicators to be scored, which then enables progress to be monitored over time. The PASS-ITT is not a replacement for the METT as individual PAs management effectiveness will still be monitored using the METT, rather the PASS-ITT (with METT scores being one indicator) will monitor the effectiveness of the PA System as a whole.”

Table 4. Key Performance Indicators identified in The National Standards and Key Performance Indicators for Antigua and Barbuda’s Protected Areas.

Component – IUCN Green List	Key Performance Indicators
Good Governance	1. An advisory /co-ordination committee comprising, government, NGO, civil society, communities and other key stakeholders, in particular women and marginalized groups established for each PA.
	2. A protected areas system co-ordination body established that allows public membership.
	3. PA declarations and availability of draft management plans advertised to public and public allowed a period of 30 days to respond/comment.
	4. Key documents and reports available and are understandable to the public.
	5. An easy to access online grievance system established to hear and resolve complaints, disputes or grievances related to PA governance or management.
Sound Planning and Design	6. Proposed Areas for Protection screened for inclusion as per national standards.
	7. 17% of land and 10% of the Marine environment covered by some form of effective protection.
	8. Antigua and Barbuda's ecosystem types, habitats, species and cultural attributes are represented in the Protected Areas System.
	9. A Protected Areas System Plan developed in participation with key stakeholders.
	10. All PAs have a relevant and comprehensive Management Plan developed in collaboration with stakeholders that is being implemented.
	11. Detailed assessments on PA values, threats and socio-economic context carried out for each PA and considered in management plan objectives.
	12. All PAs correctly assigned a IUCN Category.
Effective Management	13. Sufficient and appropriate PA legislation and policy
	14. A clear set of guidelines for permitted and prohibited activities developed for each PA in collaboration with stakeholders and PA users.
	15. A clear enforcement policy with penalties and fines developed and being implemented.
	16. Entrance fees are being collected across all PAs.
	17. At least EC\$ 1 million revenue generated by PAs or national financing strategies annually for the SIRF Fund PA thematic window.

	18. Financial sustainability score card score at least > 80% by 2031.
	19. PAME scores >75% for each PA by 2031.
	20. Management plans and progress are reviewed periodically and findings available to public and incorporated into PA planning.
	21. National and regional land use plans consider the PA System, its values and stakeholders.
	22. Smaller individual PAs have been incorporated into larger management units.
	23. Permits, access control and licensing procedures developed, implemented and are widely known by users.
	24. Visitor services identified and infrastructure plan developed and implemented for the PA system.
	25. Visitor numbers do not exceed carrying capacity of the PAs and resource harvesting does not exceed sustainable harvest levels.
	26. PA managers and tour operators meet annually to share plans, information and guidelines for PA visitation.
	27. Resource use across the PA system is thoroughly understood.
Conservation Outcomes	28. Livelihoods in harmony with nature in or near PAs are supported and enhanced.
	29. Ecosystem services conserved.
	30. Invasive and alien species are eliminated in PAs.
	31. Threats are reduced as per PA ecological and threat monitoring indicators.
	32. Habitats, species populations, ecological process and cultural sites inside PAs remain intact or their status improved.
<p>Based on Socioeconomic Concerns in Coastal Areas</p> <p>A set of guidelines for establishing a socioeconomic monitoring programme (SocMon) at a coastal management site in the Caribbean was developed in 2003 based on earlier work by the Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network. SocMon is intended to provide a methodology for regularly collecting basic socioeconomic data useful for coastal management at the site level; and to provide a basis for a regional system by which site-level data can feed into national, regional and international databases for comparison.</p> <p>SocMon utilizes 60 socioeconomic variables which guides its data collection through key informant interviews, secondary sources of information, surveys and observation in and around the target site. Data collected and analysed by the coastal resource management entity or a marine protected area (MPA) will help to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify threats, problems, solutions and opportunities; 	

2. Determine the importance, value and cultural significance of resources and their uses;
3. Assess positive and negative impacts of management measures;
4. Assess how the management body is doing (management effectiveness);
5. Build stakeholder participation and appropriate education and awareness programmes;
6. Verify and document assumptions of socioeconomic conditions in the area, community dynamics and stakeholder perceptions; and
7. Establish a baseline household and community profile.

The details on how to use the SocMon Caribbean methodology is available at:

https://www.cavehill.uwi.edu/cermes/projects/caribbean-challenge-socmon/pub/books/socmon_cm_guidelines_bunce_and_pomeroy_2003.aspx

How Should We Monitor PAs?

In preparation to undertake any monitoring activity, the PA management entity must first decide on the purpose or objectives for monitoring a selected site, ecosystem, resource or species. Based on these objectives, the details on what should be monitored has to be agreed, as well as how often and when the data needs to be collected, stored, analysed and reported. The cost of data collection should also be estimated and itemized.

Data collection is often done by a team of persons with expertise in research, personnel trained in data collection and administration of surveys, or by individuals with a keen interest in a particular resource or species. In addition to having a robust methodology for monitoring, the Team Leader and most members of the team should be highly motivated, interested in the subject matter, and dedicated to carrying out the tasks in a timely and thorough manner.

A database should be created with the contact information of people and their areas of expertise, related to habitats, species or natural resources. These persons should then be contacted to determine their interest and availability in partnering with the PA entity to participate in a monitoring programme. Where project or donor funding is available for the monitoring programme, recruitment of personnel with needed expertise outside of the PA entity could be procured. Where such funding is not readily available, negotiation to get some voluntary inputs that is convenient to the expertise needed, should be tried.

Private citizens, hobbyists/naturalists and NGOs often make detailed observations on a range of species and habitats...referred to as citizen science. These efforts could be organized by the PA management entity in support of the monitoring programme. Below is an overview of the key factors that should be considered when planning for citizen science approaches (Table 5) as proposed by the BiodivERsA Citizen Science Toolkit For Biodiversity Scientists (2020).

Table 5. Key factors that should be considered when planning for citizen science approaches extracted from the BiodivERsA Citizen Science Toolkit For Biodiversity Scientists (2020).

Key Factors	Key Considerations
Define and understand the volunteers	• Who are they?
	• Why would they want to get involved?
	• How will you reach, recruit, and retain them?
	• Does the task you want them to undertake fit their motivations?
Data quality	• What quality is needed?
	• What knowledge and training will participants need? Does this fit the volunteer profile you are aiming for?
	• Building data checks into the system
Practical considerations	• Is the time commitment needed to set-up a Citizen Science system, recruit and train volunteers etc. worth the return you are likely to get?
	• Do you have the resources for marketing, communication and volunteer support needed to run a successful project?
	• Partner with experienced Citizen Science organisations (i.e. NGOs)
	• What are the ethical implications?

Minimum Parameters for Monitoring

At a minimum, if no monitoring of the PA site has been done, then the following parameters in Table 6 are suggested (Homer, 2019) in addition to any other elements as required in the management plan for the site.

Table 6. Minimum parameters for monitoring at a protected area.

Parameter	Comments
Disturbance	identify the extent and severity of any disturbance including pest and disease, human activity, fire or extreme climatic events (flooding, drought, etc.).
Water Quality	determine clarity/turbidity, flowing/stagnant, depth, debris, composition of stream floor (mud, gravel, boulders, etc.).
Aquatic and Marine Fauna	determine if any fish and crustacean are present, their abundance and the number of different species observed.
Avifauna	determine abundance and species richness of birds seen or heard.
Other fauna	identify any signs of mammals, reptiles, amphibians and insects.
Flora	ground cover, canopy cover and dominant species (e.g. 'big trees', herbaceous plants, etc. and abundance). Note any plants flowering, fruiting, etc.
Corals/Algae/Sponges	identify general composition and structure of habitat, including number of different species and species abundance.

Visitor Use	number of visitors at sites with heavy use (hotspots); type of visitor use at key sites; duration of visit at specific sites, visitor impacts e.g. litter, pollution, soil compaction/erosion, damage to plants/habitat etc.
Note: Species abundance changes as a function of changes in the physical environment and in interactions among species in a local assemblage. Wherever possible the relative abundance of the most common species at the site should be recorded.	

What should we do with the data collected?

Ideally, all data collected from the PA monitoring programme should also be copied to a central data repository for storage, later retrieval, analysis and the provision of information products as required by stakeholders. Within the Department of Environment, the Monitoring, Evaluation and Data Management Unit (DMU) is responsible for the monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of environmental projects, coordinating field data collection, managing environmental databases and coordinating environmental data-driven projects (Department of Environment, 2020c). The DMU has established and manages the following databases and will have the lead role in the National Environmental Data & Information System (NEIS):

- Environmental Information Management and Advisory System (EIMAS)/Natural Resource Inventory
- Environment Registry
- Environment Statistics Database

Data from all PA monitoring efforts should therefore be copied to the DMU. The DMU should be involved in all PA monitoring efforts, including assistance in ensuring data quality assurance and quality control and formatting for ease of data entry.

Conclusion

The expectation is that this document will be used as a guide by PA Managers to develop their own monitoring programme based on the components outlined in the previous sections, the PA's priorities and existing resource constraints. Any aspect of the various elements previously identified can be modified to suit, site specific needs. PA Managers and Monitoring Teams may find it useful to study the guidance documents contained in the References of this report.

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